

Design of a Ground Station for a Kite Power System

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Acronyms

AC	alternating current
airborne wind energy	airborne wind energy
ASSET	Institute for Applied Sustainable Science Engineering and Technology
CEM	clutch coupled electrical machine concept
CGCM	clutch coupled generator and motor concept
CGRM	clutch coupled generator and rigidly connected motor concept
DC	direct current
REM	rigidly connected electrical machine concept
RGCM	rigidly connected generator and clutch coupled motor concept
RGRM	rigidly connected generator and motor concept
UHMWPE	ultra-high-molecular-weight polyethylene

Chapter 1 Introduction

1.1 Pumping Kite Power Generation

“The higher regions of the atmosphere, where, when the winds sleep below, there are powerful and steady currents of air rapidly floating.” [Poc27]

This insight sparked the resolve at the end of the 20th century to harvest wind energy at high altitudes¹. With the publication of “Crosswind Kite Power” in 1980 by Miles L. Loyd, research in this field took off. Since then, a steadily growing number of institutions worldwide have been striving for the breakthrough to harvest the strong and steady winds at high altitudes to produce electricity using airborne wind energy (airborne wind energy) systems (see Figure 1-1).

Figure 1-1.: *Number of institutions actively involved in airborne wind energy. Based on [Fur10].*

By using tethered flying devices instead of ground-based wind turbines, material can be significantly saved since no tower is needed. These savings account for 21% of the total material costs of a wind turbine [Hau05, p. 711]. The resulting lower environmental impact² and the suitability for mobile deployment are additional benefits, which support the exploitation in the growing wind energy market.

A kite attached to a ground station with a tether, operating in a “pumping cycle” (see Figure 1-2), is one of several concepts that promise low costs for renewable energy. The main advantage of this concept in comparison to others in this field is the placement of

¹The term “high altitudes” refers to heights which cannot be reached by conventional wind turbines (currently 200 m).

²The environmental impact summarizes the effects on the environment during production (e. g. CO₂-emissions) and operation (e. g. the visual impact).

most of its components (for instance the generator) on the ground. Weight is less critical there and maintenance more convenient than in other approaches.

Figure 1-2.: *The pumping cycle: The kite flies cross wind during the reel-out phase (above) and is retrieved during the reel-in phase with different angle of attack (below)[Sch11a].*

While the Skysails GmbH already operates automatically controlled kites on ships for additional traction with a power equivalent of 1-2 MW [Sky11], the conversion of wind power into electricity by kites is still far from these magnitudes.

A kite power system with a generator capacity of 18.5 kW has been in testing at Delft University of Technology since 2010. Despite its power rating, the average electrical output power achieved so far is amere 6.5 kW (measured over one cycle). Due to this high electrical crest factor³, the kite power system is not capable of taking advantage of its increased full load hours when compared to conventional wind turbines⁴. The increase of the full load hours results from the adaptable height and therefore higher utilization of the kite power system in fluctuating wind conditions.

1.2 Goal of the Thesis

The electrical output of the kite power system shall be increased from 6.5 kW to 20 kW during operation. Two approaches are pursued to achieve this goal. Firstly, the capacity of the generator has to be increased and secondly, the total efficiency of the kite power system has to be improved. Therefore, weak spots in the existing ground station have

³The electrical crest factor is defined as the ratio of the electrical net power of the system and the nominal capacity of the generator.

⁴The full load hours for the kite power system and wind turbines are defined in the Glossary.

to be detected and losses of its elements⁵ reduced. Thus the question to be answered is:

“How must a new transportable⁶ ground station for a kite power system, operating in a pumping cycle, be designed to provide an average electrical output of 20 kW during operation while its total efficiency is improved?”

The improvement of the ground station is one prerequisite for demonstrating the potential of competitive energy costs⁷ of the kite power system, which in turn will determine the market segments that can be entered with this technology.

1.3 Methodology and Structure of the Thesis

The *munich procedure model* is the methodology used in this thesis. It was developed at the Technical University of Munich on the basis of the “procedure for development and construction (VDI 2221)”⁸, the V-Model for the Design of Mechatronical Systems (VDI 2206), the “problem solving cycle of system engineering”, and the “approach cycle” according to Ehrlenspiel [Lin09, p. 46]. It combines the main ideas of these prior models but eliminates their possible weaknesses while offering compatibility between them [Lin09, p. 46]. In Figure 1-3, the seven steps of the *munich procedure model* are shown. Each step poses three to five central questions to guide the user through the development process (see Appendix A.1) [Lin09, p. 46].

Figure 1-3.: *The standard procedure of the Munich Procedure Model. The overlapping circles show that the steps are not always clearly distinguishable.*

⁵Elements comprise parts, components, assemblies, and subsystem of the kite power system (see also Glossary).

⁶The reasons why it must be transportable are discussed in Section 2.2.

⁷The energy costs take all costs during the product life cycle into account.

⁸The VDI (Verein Deutscher Ingenieure) is the Association of German Engineers.

In the step, *goal planning*, the development situation is analyzed and influences on the product are determined. The requirements of the product are defined in the step *goal analysis*. *Task structuring* describes the system abstractly to formulate design goals independently of familiar solutions. In the next step, *generation of solution ideas*, recognized solutions are collected and new solutions generated. The alternatives arrived at are analyzed in the step *properties assessment*. *Decision making* evaluates the alternative solutions on the basis of the determined properties. The last step, *ensuring goal achievement*, identifies and minimizes risks at the end of the development process.

One of the main advantages over other models is the flexible usage. The *munich procedure model* allows alternative ways, iterations, and recursive application of the seven basic steps [Lin09, p. 46 ff.]. In Figure 1-4, the application of the *munich procedure model* in this thesis on three levels is visualized.

Figure 1-4.: *Adapted procedure of the Munich Procedure Model for the design of the ground station. The ground station is on the highest level, the generator concept and the tether guidance.*

The ground station is discussed as a whole (on the highest level) in Chapter 2. *Goal planning* describes the design task abstractly, includes the kite power system of which the ground station is a part, and reviews the ground station currently used. In the *goal analysis*, the requirements are derived from the purpose and constraints of the ground station. An abstract system definition, the identification of degrees of freedom of the design process, and recommended actions are part of the *task structuring*.

In Chapter 3, the generator concept, which is a subordinated element of the ground station, is examined. Therefore, the steps, *goal planning*, *goal analysis*, and *task structuring*

are carried out on a second level for the ground station. For developing of solution ideas, the concept is broken down into subconcepts, and the steps, *generation of solution ideas*, *properties assessment*, and *decision making* are executed on a third level of the *munich procedure model*⁹. In a synthesis, these subconcepts are combined and the same three steps carried out for the generator concept (again on the second level).

The tether guidance is examined in Chapter 4. As in the previous chapter, the first steps of the *munich procedure model* are carried out for the tether guidance as a whole (on the second level) until the different elements have been identified. The *munich procedure model* steps, *generation of solution ideas*, *properties assessment*, and *decision making* are then carried out for these subordinated elements on the third level before suitable tether guidance concepts are evaluated in a synthesis (second level).

In Chapter 5, focus is on the ground station in its entirety again (highest level). The step, *ensuring goal achievement* evaluates interdependencies of the two discussed concepts and possible goal deviations.

In Chapter 6, the methodology used is reviewed with regard to its application on the design of the ground station and its usage in the context of a thesis.

The results of the thesis are summarized and recommendations for further research are given in the last chapter.

⁹For the gearbox *goal analysis* is also carried out.

Chapter 2 Ground Station - Goal Planning, Goal Analysis and Task Structuring

2.1 Goal Planning

Goal planning is the first step to be executed within the *munich procedure model* and provides an overview of the development situation. In the following paragraphs, the design task is defined, the kite power system of the Technical University of Delft is described, and the existing ground station is reviewed. This will provide the necessary information to define the requirements for a new ground station in the following step *goal analysis*.

The following fields were analyzed as to their influences on the product development process:

- design task,
- system definition, and
- review of the current ground station.

2.1.1 Design Task

To develop a product that is technically and economically successful, three questions have to be answered at the beginning of the design process [Lin10, l. 3, s. 4]:

- What exactly is the objective of the design process?
- Who are the customers who are willing to purchase the product?
- In which market will the product be launched?

Here, the *objective* of the product design process is to develop a new ground station for the kite power system of the Technical University of Delft on the basis of the existing one (see Section 2.1.3). It has to be transportable and independent of a grid connection and shall be used to test the kite control unit¹ of the research group. The aim is to increase the ground station's electrical net power and total efficiency². Furthermore, the ground station shall provide possibilities to address various research questions, such as the further development of the kite control unit, enhancement of the kite design, and optimization of

¹The kite control unit is the flying device underneath the kite that steers the kite during operation (see also Section 2.1.2.)

²The total efficiency is defined in Appendix A.8.

the automatic control for the kite and the ground station. Besides the technical objectives, also economic aspects have to be taken into account to attract development partners and investors to evolve the kite power system into a marketable product. It must be proved that a kite power system can produce electrical power at competitive costs according to the market segment you want to enter. The ground station shall serve as the basis for a small series production of off-grid power generation systems (see below)³.

The first - internal⁴ - *customer* is the kite power research group from the Institute for Applied Sustainable Science Engineering and Technology (ASSET) at the Technical University of Delft. The objectives of the research group are to bring the kite power system to attention as a chance to extract energy from the - so far - unreachable source of atmospheric air flows lowering the share of fossil energy sources in power generation and to educate students in this field. Skysails, “eco-resorts”, operators of “eco-sailing”, and other research groups can be counted as potential external customers [Sch11b, p. 7]. The aims of these customers reach from large scale power generation over use of the kite power system as a representative figurehead, to a tool for research on various open questions in the field of airborne wind energy.

The *markets* to be addressed for a kite power system are, on the one hand, off-grid wind energy for remote or disaster areas and, on the other hand, large-scale offshore wind energy. Both market segments have unique requirements which have to be fulfilled (e. g. different orders of magnitude). While offshore applications require large scales to lower energy costs, decentralized energy generation is rather small-scaled and can permit higher energy costs if infrastructure - like the power grid - can be omitted. The development should focus on the latter market segment to reduce the time to market, aiming for a small-scaled kite power system.

2.1.2 The Kite Power System

Pumping Operation

The kite power system operates in a pumping cycle which consists of distinct phases - reel-out, reel-in and an upper and lower transition. In the reel-out phase, the kite generates lift through dynamic crosswind maneuvers and draws the tether from the drum at the ground station (see Figure 1-2). In the ground station, an electrical machine - operated in generator mode⁵ - is connected to the drum and converts the mechanical into electrical power. The energy generated during the reel-out phase is stored in a battery. In the reel-in phase, a part of this energy is used to retrieve the kite, operating the same electrical machine as motor. By changing the angle of attack, the effort for retrieving is significantly lesser than the benefit of the reel-out phase (see Figure 2-1). This difference

³The adaption of manufacturing methods due to production quantity is beyond the focus of this thesis.

⁴The customer is defined as internal since it is directly involved in the development process.

⁵Electrical machines can be operated in generator or motor mode.

enables the system to have a positive power output over one cycle. Between the reel-out and reel-in phases, transition phases are present in which the elevation angle of the kite is changed without reeling-in or reeling-out to adjust the position of the kite for the subsequent phase. The kite is controlled by the kite control unit, which steers left-right and changes the angle of attack. A single tether⁶ leads the force from the kite control unit to the ground station in which the mechanical power is converted to electrical power as described above (see Figure 1-2).

Figure 2-1.: *Mechanical power during five cycles [Sch11a]. During the reel-out phases power is supplied which is displayed as positive power, during the reel-in phase power is consumed (negative power).*

Description of Elements of the Kite Power System

The kite power system is broken down into subsystems, assemblies, components, and parts which are all defined as elements⁷ to describe the kite power system and the relationship between its' elements [vT06, p. 1-6].

The kite power system consists of the two subsystems: ground station and kite control unit, three assemblies: control stand, tether, and kite, and two components: wind sensor and communication module (see Figure A-1 in Appendix A.3). The tether, kite control unit, and kite are airborne elements while the other elements are located on the ground.

Before the ground station is analyzed in Section 2.1.3, the other elements of the kite power system are described in the following paragraphs. Pictures of the elements can be found in Appendix A.19.

⁶The advantage of a single tether is the reduced drag when compared to a steering concept in which several tethers connect the kite with the ground station, omitting the flying kite control unit.

⁷The classification of an element is based on its complexity.

The *kite* converts the power of the wind into a lifting force and a translational power of the tether⁸. It works comparable to the wing of a plane, generating lift by means of an aerodynamic profile. In contrast to a wing, the kite is inflatable with a flexible structure which reduces weight and storage space during transportation but the lift-over-drag ratio does not reach the level of a rigid wing. Different kites are currently used: a 25 m² kite is used regularly, but also 50 m² and 14 m² kites have been already tested⁹. The bridle¹⁰ of the kite is connected to the kite control unit.

The *kite control unit* controls the lengths of the two power lines and the two steering lines with two motors. One motor powers and depowers the kite, and the other steers the kite left-right. The kite control unit is linked through a tether (see below) to the ground station. Two integrated batteries deliver energy to drive the motors for a period of up to two hours. The assembly of the kite control unit is shown in Figure 2-2. The mechanical design was done by the SMI groep¹¹ with input from ASSET. The control was developed by ASSET itself.

Figure 2-2.: *The kite control unit*

The *tether* leads the force from the kite to the ground station. It is 4 mm in diameter and made out of ultra-high-molecular-weight polyethylene (UHMWPE) - developed from DSM Dyneema[®] - with a total length of 1,000 m. The tether has a weak link underneath the kite control unit, which has a breaking force of 6 kN \pm 10%, and a rope cutter above the pod, which can be activated from the control stand. There is also a 1.2 kN absorber in a safety line which is a 2.5 mm strong UHMWPE tether with a breaking resistance of 6 kN and a 15 m extra rope to smooth down the shock if the weak link breaks. The

⁸The transmitted mechanical power is the product of the lifting force of the kite and the tether speed.

⁹For comparison: Standard surf kites have a surface between 5 m² and 15 m². The kites which are used by Skysails to pull vessels have a surface of 160 m² and 320 m².

¹⁰The bridle leads the forces acting at the kite to the steering and power lines.

¹¹The SMI groep is a company in Dokkum, Netherlands, which has its focus in metal working and contract manufacturing for offshore applications.

tether itself was bought off-the-shelf from Lankhorst, the adjustments were made by ASSET.

The *control stand* provides the user interface for two persons who are responsible for steering the kite and controlling the ground station (see Figures 2-3 and 2-4).

Figure 2-3.: The kite control user interface

Figure 2-4.: The ground station control user interface

The *wind sensor* measures the local wind speed at 6 m height to link the mechanical and electrical power to the wind velocity. The *communication module* transmits the control information from the ground station to the kite control unit and vice versa.

2.1.3 Review of the Existing Ground Station

After the other elements of the kite power system have been described, the existing ground station is reviewed to determine possible improvements. The ground station was built by Machinefabriek ÉMCE¹² at the request of ASSET for 60,000 Euro in 2009 to test their kite control units and kites. In January 2010 the ground station was first tested. Since then, over 20 test days with more than 30 hours of operation time have been absolved. The requirements of the ground station were derived from the self-built prototype built in 2007.

Original Requirements

The documentation of requirements by ÉMCE was not a specific contract agreement with ASSET to reduce working hours and costs. Therefore only a short list of requirements is documented [EMC09, p. 1]: For a tether diameter of 4.5 mm, the drum had to have a capacity of 11 km¹³. The tether velocity had to reach 4 m/s for the reel-out phase and 8

¹²Machinefabriek ÉMCE is a manufacturer of winches and part of the Stokvis Holding Group with head office in Voorhout Holland. [EMC]

¹³Because the ground station also should provide the possibility to set a world record as the highest flying kite, it had to have a capacity of 20 km for a 3 mm tether.

Figure 2-5.: CAD drawing of the ground station [EMC10]

Figure 2-6.: Scheme of the current ground station [Fec11a]

m/s for the reel-in phase. The maximum reel-in force had to reach 1.5 kN¹⁴. The ground station had to operate without grid connection with a battery capacity of 10 kWh. The maximum weight of the ground station including trailer was not to exceed 2,800 kg so it could be pulled by a car [dW11].

Description of the Existing Ground Station

The elements subordinated to the ground station are shown in Figure A-2 in Appendix A.3. The elements are classified according to their discipline: mechanics and electromechanics, electronics, and information technology (see Figure 2-7) according to [Ise05, p. 5].

Figure 2-7.: Mechatronic disciplines [Ise05, p. 5]

The elements of the ground station and their subelements are described in the following paragraphs. The level of detail is oriented at the disposability of the elements. On the

¹⁴In the original document, forces are given in kilogram-force (kgf). For unambiguous units, in this thesis forces are always given in Newton (N).

lowest level, all elements shall be able to be purchased from suppliers. Pictures of the ground station elements can be found in Appendix A.19.

The mechanical elements are the tether guidance, the drive train, the body work and the trailer. The electromechanical elements are the EM and the sled.

The *tether guidance* is comprised of the swivel, which leads the tether into the ground station¹⁵, the pulley, which redirects the tether to the drum, and the drum itself which converts the linear movement of the tether into a rotation of the shaft and vice versa and stores the tether (see Figure 2-8).

Figure 2-8.: *Elements of the tether guidance*

The *drive train* leads the mechanical power of the drum to the generator. It consists of the drum shaft connected to the drum, a driving belt¹⁶ in between the belt pulleys on the drum shaft and the gearing shaft, a planetary gearing, which reduces torque and increases the rotation speed with a transmission ratio of 1:6.2 towards the electrical machine shaft, which is connected to the generator¹⁷.

Figure 2-9.: *Elements of the drive train*

The *body work* is defined as the structural assembly of the frame and the control cabinet, which encases other elements (e. g. the motor controllers). It provides stiffness to support the torque of the drive train, arrange the elements, and protect them from external influences (see Figure 2-10).

¹⁵An illustration of the swivel is shown in the Appendix.

¹⁶The driving belt has no transmission but is only used to transmit the torque to a second shaft to reduce the total length of the drive train.

¹⁷A brake that permits deceleration at the end of the reel-out phase with a maximum braking torque of 300 Nm is not included in Figure 2-8.

Figure 2-10.: *Elements of the body work*

The *trailer* enables the ground station to be pulled by a car and provides therefore the mobility of the kite power system. Since this component is an off-the-shelf product it need not be further subdivided.

The *electrical machine* (Type: Lafert, ST 180M C4) is a three-phase squirrel cage induction machine and has a power capacity of 18.5 kW [Laf]. The power factor $\cos(\phi)$ is 0.80 at the nominal rotation speed of 1,440 rpm in motor operation. The nominal speed in generator operation is 1,720 rpm. It is designed for a range of rated voltage from 380 V AC to 420 V AC with a frequency of 50 Hz $\pm 5\%$. The maximum frequency of operation is 95 Hz (provided by the motor controller). It is IP-54 certified and can accelerate the tether up to 0.5 m/s^2 . The maximum tether velocity for reel-in and reel-out is 8 m/s. The electrical machine is controlled via the control stand (see Section 2.1.2). Generally, the tether velocity during the reel-out phase is set to one third of the wind speed. If the force measured at the load cell (see below) exceeds a preset value¹⁸, the control is force-driven and the reel-out speed is adapted accordingly¹⁹. The maximum retention force, which can be held by the electrical machine, is 8 kN. Since this component is bought off-the-shelf it needs not to be further subdivided.

The *sled* moves the drum to ensure a right angle of the tether when coiled on the drum. It moves on slide bearings on two holms attached to the body work and is driven by a spindle motor with a capacity of 2.75 kW. The frame of the sled acts as support structure for the drum, drive train, and electrical machine.

The electronic assemblies are the energy storage and the power infrastructure.

The *energy storage* accepts energy during the reel-out phase and provides it during the reel-in phase - independently of a grid connection - to retrieve the kite. It consists of 104 lithium cells²⁰ with a total capacity of 18 kWh and a voltage of 350 V DC. The

¹⁸The preset value is generally 3.5 kN. The maximum force the system - more precisely the kite - can withstand is 4 kN.

¹⁹In Appendix A.15, the dependency of tether force and tether speed is given.

²⁰Before 104 lead-acid cells with the same capacity had been integrated.

Figure 2-11.: *Elements of the sled*

balancer boards, connected to each battery cell, measure the voltage and dissipate power when the cells are fully charged to prevent overload. Further, there is a secondary battery to stabilize the voltage of the 240 V DC-bus²¹ (see Figure 2-12).

Figure 2-12.: *Elements of the energy storage*

The *power infrastructure* consists of the motor controllers for the electrical machine and the spindle motor, the load cell, an inverter to power the control stand, one converter to power the brakes²², one converter to power the load cell and encoders of the motor controller²³, the varistor to dissipate power²⁴, and cables. The motor controllers have sensors and inverters integrated to measure the state of the machines and provide them with the corresponding voltage, current, and frequency²⁵ (see Figure A-3 in Appendix A.3).

The only computing assembly is the IT infrastructure.

The *IT infrastructure* enables the data transfer from one element to the other and pro-

²¹The 240 V DC-bus provides power to the control stand.

²²The maximum current for the brakes is 20 A.

²³The maximum current for the load cell and encoders is 20 A.

²⁴Power has to be dissipated when the electrical power from the generator exceeds the charging limits of the battery or the batteries are fully loaded to prevent overload.

²⁵The sensors and inverters are not shown in the diagram since the motor controllers are the components to purchase.

cesses the data. The programmable logic controller²⁶ processes the encoder and load cell data. The I/O-module centralizes the links between the elements. An expansion adapter extends the capacity of the programmable logic controller. Cables and wireless links connect the different elements (see Figure 2-13).

Figure 2-13.: *Elements of the IT infrastructure*

The links of ground station elements are shown in Figure A-4 in Appendix A.3 with their physical and power connections.

2.2 Goal Analysis

In the last section, the kite power system as a whole and the ground station explicitly have been discussed. In this section, the general requirements for the ground station are derived from the design objective and the constraints and predefined properties to ensure that the objective of the design process is achieved. At the end of this section, the requirements are documented and their potential discrepancies identified.

Systems engineering proposes three consecutive tasks to determine the requirements of an element [vT06, p. 6-2]:

- define the purpose of the element and its constraints,
- derive the general requirements of the element from its purpose and constraints, and
- break down the requirements until all subordinated elements have been defined.

The first two tasks are carried out for the ground station in this section, while the third task is addressed in the following chapters, where the critical subordinated elements are discussed.

²⁶In literature the programmable logic controller is mostly abbreviated with “PLC”.

2.2.1 Purpose

The purpose of the ground station is defined as follows:

“The ground station shall prove the technical and economic feasibility of a pumping cycle with kites as the chosen airborne wind energy concept.”

The purpose can be subdivided into technical and economical aspects. The technical aspects include the use of the ground station as a demonstration object for stakeholders. It must provide a positive energy balance in operation. Further it shall be used as a research object to optimize the concept. The economic aspects cover the costs of the phases development, production, operation, and recycling²⁷ [HTML09]. In Figure A-6 in Appendix A.4 the purposes are shown. The costs are subdivided into:

- development costs (include the costs for the prototype),
- production costs (for a small series),
- operation costs, and
- recycling costs.

These costs can be summarized to life cycle costs from which the costs of energy can be derived²⁸. The costs of energy determine the market scope (see Chapter 2.1.1).

2.2.2 Constraints

Internal and external constraints have influence on the requirements. Internal constraints include technical aspects²⁹, safety, and resources, like time, costs, and facilities. External constraints are given by aeronautical authorities and the street traffic regulation (see Figure A-7 in Appendix A.4).

It should be mentioned that the various constraints are not relevant in the same phase of the product life cycle. While the internal constraints mainly influence development and production, street traffic regulation has to be taken into account for transportation, and aeronautical authorities have their interests centered on the operation phase. Nevertheless, all these constraints must be considered in the development phase.

²⁷The product life cycle phases are given in Appendix A.18.

²⁸This is beyond the focus of this thesis.

²⁹Technical constraints are defined as technical solutions that have to be used to implement the concept. Therefore they are regarded as internal. Technical constraints could also be defined as today's technical possibilities in general but would then be regarded as external.

2.2.3 Requirements Definition

The requirements are derived from the purpose and constraints and are structured according to their source. The checklist, *clarification of requirements*, decreases the chance of neglecting important requirements³⁰. In Appendix A.4, this checklist is shown. The majority of requirements are not quantified, as there is yet no general framework of stakeholders, resources, and other conditions of the product development process which have influence on their quantification. However, an overview of the general requirements assists in the comprehension of the system and its development process.

Demonstration Object and Street Traffic Regulations

The kite power system shall be used as a demonstration object for stakeholders in different locations. Therefore it must be transportable³¹. To be transportable it must be assured that operation without grid connection is possible, thus an energy storage is required. Due to street traffic regulations, the weight of the trailer must not exceed 2,800 kg and the dimensions of car and trailer must not exceed 12 m x 2.55 m x 4 m. For convenient transportation, no special permission (e. g. for dangerous goods) should be required.

Provide Electricity

The kite power system shall provide electricity. Therefore, the mechanical power of the tether must be converted by an electrical machine into electrical power, which has to be either stored in the batteries or fed into the grid³². In this thesis, the focus lies in the storage of electrical energy, since the first application will be off-the-grid (see Section 2.1.1).

Optimization of the Concept

It is the goal of the kite power research group at ASSET to develop the concept of a pumping cycle with kites. This entails the following requirements: Due to the fact that a tethered kite has to be used in the given concept, a drum must be part of the ground station for coiling the tether³³. The diameter of this tether is determined by the force which the tether has to stand, and it influences the geometry of the tether guidance.

³⁰Checklists can never be complete. Therefore, the use of a checklist is no guarantee that all important requirements have been met.

³¹For the transport the existing car (VW Crafter pickup van) shall be used to tow the ground station on a trailer.

³²Other possibilities of the mechanical to electrical conversion are discussed in [Sch11c] and are therefore not considered in this thesis.

³³Other means of the translational to rotational conversion are discussed in [Sch11c] and are therefore not considered in this thesis.

The desired tether force determines a corresponding torque at the drum dependant on the drum diameter. The winch must be auto-controllable to decrease the need of manual control. The rotation of the drum must be reversible and controllable to execute a full cycle with its reel-out and reel-in phase. To reduce losses when reversing the rotation direction, the inertia of the drum should be minimized. For further improvement and to survey the ground station during operation, the states of the kite, kite control unit, and ground station must be measured, displayed, and tracked.

Economic Feasibility and Resources

To achieve economical feasibility, costs must be limited. Development costs are limited by the resources of the kite power research group. Therefore automatic launching and landing will not be an integrated function of the ground station³⁴. To minimize production costs of a small series, it is mandatory that these costs be considered in the prototype phase. Operation and recycling costs are essential for the market success when compared to other competitive technologies and concepts.

Technical Constraints

There are various technical constraints placed on this concept. A drum must be used to coil the tether. The tether must be spread to define its position and angle towards the drum during reel-out and reel-in phase. A generator must be used to convert mechanical into electrical power. The energy storage must be a set of Li-batteries, which the kite power research group already possesses.

Safety

Safety can be seen as an external or internal constraint, since, on the one hand, safety regulations are set down by law, and, on the other hand, safety is also a concern of the kite power research group. Here safety is regarded as internal due to its more direct influence. Harm to humans and damage to material must be avoided. An emergency stop must be integrated, and the tether must be releasable. Redundancy of functions ensures safe operation.

Aeronautical Authorities

Aeronautical authorities allow a maximum flight height of 500 m above ground at the test site in Valkenburg. The flight height indirectly influences parameters of the ground station (e. g. drum capacity and rotation speed).

³⁴This requirement is listed because it was planned to integrate automated launching and landing, but due to resource issues, it is no longer intended.

2.2.4 Requirement Discrepancies

Conflicting requirements have to be pointed out. These conflicts have to be either solved by finding a solution to satisfy all requirements or by favoring one of the requirements and neglecting the other [Lin09, p. XY]. The consistency matrix in Appendix A.4.3 displays these interdependencies.

Due to the hierarchic structure of the requirements, there are several interdependencies between parents and children³⁵ which do not have to be considered. However some conflicts exist. The use of a generator has a negative interrelation to the size and weight of the ground station. This has to be considered when solutions are proposed and evaluated. Moreover, the use of an energy storage can have a negative influence on the transportability, since batteries represent a potential danger in traffic. Close attention is paid to costs in the following chapters, since several requirements conflict with them.

It can be concluded that none of the interrelations between requirements demand a decision to favor one requirement over another. The size, weight, and costs have to be considered in the design process.

2.3 Task Structuring

In the previous section the requirements have been defined. Now the process to achieve the design objective has to be determined. Therefore the functions of the ground station are structured on an abstract level by means of the *relation function model*. This prevents an early fixation on recognized solutions ideas. The core action points have to be identified to focus the process on critical elements. At the end of this section precise goals are formulated to enable the *generation of solution ideas* in the following section [Lin09, p. 48].

2.3.1 Abstract System Definition

The development of the *relation function model* can be found in Appendix A.7. The functions are categorized in the following paragraphs as primary, secondary, and tertiary functions.

³⁵A child is an item which is subordinated to a parent item.

Primary Functions of the Kite Power System

The five primary - or main - functions of the kite power system³⁶ are shown in Figure 2-14; they are the ones desired in the first place³⁷. All other functions either support them or are caused by them.

Figure 2-14.: *Primary functions of the kite power system*

Initially, the wind power must be harvested. That is to say: the kinetic power of the flowing air must be extracted and transformed into a force acting at the tether and a movement of it³⁸. This power has to be delivered to the ground station so it can be used. The conversion of translational power into rotational power is necessary to enable the following conversion into electrical power³⁹. In the end, the electrical energy has to be stored⁴⁰.

Secondary Functions of the Ground Station

Secondary functions either enable primary functions or are caused by them. As said before, the tether must be reeled-out to transfer the mechanical power to the ground station. The guiding and coiling of the tether support the conversion from translational into rotational power. Due to the control of torque, rotation speed, current, voltage, and frequency, the mechanical power can be converted into electrical power. By controlling the current and voltage of the batteries, electrical energy can be stored. The conversion into electrical power and the storage of energy enable to provide electrical power. The transport of power to the ground station causes wear of the tether, oscillations in the tether, and overloads. The conversion from translational into rotational power causes mechanical friction and a loss of mechanical power. Electrical losses are caused by the conversion into electrical power and the storage of electrical energy. In Figure 2-15, the secondary functions are allocated around the primary functions with their relations to them and to each other.

³⁶To show the ground station functions in the context of the whole kite power system all primary functions of the kite power system are shown.

³⁷By definition, adverse functions cannot be primary.

³⁸Without movement no power can be transmitted.

³⁹Possibilities of the integration of the both function “convert translational into rotational power” and “convert mechanical into electrical power” into one function “convert translational into electrical power” have been discussed in [Sch11c] and are not further considered in this thesis.

⁴⁰The feed-in into the grid is not considered as primary function since the focus of the design process lies on the application of the kite power system as decentralized power system.

Figure 2-15.: Secondary functions of the ground station in relation to the primary functions

Tertiary Functions

Tertiary functions are defined as the ones which are not directly related to primary functions.

It is necessary to define the position of the tether towards the drum in order to coil the tether. The coiled tether must be stored in the ground station. The tether is bent due to the guiding, coiling, and storing, this creates internal friction and wears the tether.

Figure 2-16.: Relation function model for coiling

The friction between elements can be reduced by either decreasing the relative speed, the normal force, or the friction coefficient between the elements. The friction causes wear of the elements, but this can be lowered by an even load distribution. Damages which can occur due to wearing of elements can harm people and environment; the probability can be reduced by redundancy.

The oscillations in the tether can be reduced by means of a damping. This damping also can help to even out the load distribution.

To complete one cycle and reel-out the tether again in the subsequent cycle, it must be reeled-in again. Electrical power has to be converted into mechanical power to enable the

Figure 2-17.: *Relation function model for wear elements*

Figure 2-18.: *Relation function model for oscillations in the tether*

reel-in of the tether. The reel-in can cause the tether to loop.

Figure 2-19.: *Relation function model for reel-in*

Mechanical power has to be provided to move the tether axially to define the tether position in relationship to the drum. The axial movement prevents the tether to loop and reduces the friction of the tether which both cause tether wear.

To control and limit voltage and current of the electrical energy being stored, these parameters must be measured (and displayed), and it must be possible to decelerate the drive train⁴¹ by means of electrical power.

In Appendix A.7, the complete *relation function model* is shown.

The adverse function “lose electrical power” could be seen as redundant to the useful function “provide electrical power”. Here, “lose electrical power” is used when power is

⁴¹The drive train delivers power from the drum to the electrical machine or vice versa.

Figure 2-21.: *Relation function model for parameters*

dissipated due to resistance of leads; while “provide electrical power” is used when auxiliary systems consume power. The same applies for mechanical power where friction is regarded as loss and where the axial movement and the reel-in of the tether are considered as power consumption.

The developed *relation function model* releases the fixated view on concrete elements of the ground station and enlarge the solution space for possible design concepts. It further enables the identification of degrees of freedom in the following section.

2.3.2 Identification of Degrees of Freedom and Recommended Steps of Action

The purpose of the kite power system described at the beginning of this chapter, the secondary adverse functions examined in the last section, and the degrees of freedom which have been evaluated in the subsequent paragraph dictate the steps of action to be taken (see Figure 2-22).

The purpose of the ground station which was defined as: “The ground station shall prove the technical and economic feasibility of a pumping cycle with kites as the chosen air-borne wind energy concept.” has to be kept in mind when the steps of action are determined.

Figure 2-22.: *Deduction of steps of action*

From the *relation function model*, secondary adverse functions can be identified. These functions and the useful functions which avoid or reduce their effects are given in Figure A-18 in Appendix A.7.3. The description of these functions can be found in the prior section.

To identify degrees of freedom, the hierarchy of the current system is examined. The elements beside the ground station are not the focus of this thesis and therefore have not been considered. From the ground station elements, “tether guidance”, “drive train”, “electrical machine”, and “sled” are the most influencing elements⁴² (see dependancy matrix in Appendix A.5) and are therefore discussed in the following chapters (see Figure A-9). The other assemblies are either off-the-shelf products or passive elements which have to be adapted to the ones mentioned above.

If the secondary adverse functions are compared with the purposes in Chapter 2.2, it can be stated that power losses (mechanical and electrical) have an effect on the “optimization of the concept” and the “costs of energy”, therefore they are given the highest priority. In all four assemblies, which were identified as degrees of freedom, losses are an issue. Thus the critical elements and the functions they fulfill are:

- the electrical machine converts mechanical into electrical power,
- the drive train transmits the mechanical power and increases the rotation speed⁴³,
- the tether guidance leads the tether to the drum, and
- The sled positions the drum in relationship to the tether⁴⁴.

The four critical elements above are prioritized due the role they play in the energy losses. In Figure 2-23, the energy distribution of an example cycle is shown.

⁴²The energy storage is also an active element but is not considered here due its recent substitution.

⁴³The function “increase rotation speed” is not detected in the development of the *relation function model* since it results from constraints placed on the rotation speed of electrical machine, which was not considered in the *relation function model*. In Chapter 3, this function is integrated to determine possible design solutions.

⁴⁴The solution space is extended by integrating the sled into the tether guidance (see Chapter 4).

Figure 2-23.: *Energy distribution of one cycle*

The mechanical losses of the drive train $E_{mech,dt}$ are 18.2% of the net mechanical energy $E_{mech,cyc}$. The electrical losses of the electric machine $E_{el,EM}$ are 24.8%. The spindle motor $E_{el,spdl}$ consumes 7.3% and the brake $E_{el,brk}$ consumes 3.0% of $E_{mech,cyc}$. The total efficiency is therefore 46.7%. It is assumed that the higher the losses currently are, the bigger the leverage of improvement is and, therefore, the higher the priority to redesign the elements should be.

The following recommendations of actions are stated:

- find an appropriate solution to convert rotational into electrical power increasing the efficiency,
- guide the tether in such a way that mechanical losses are minimized,
- reduce the mechanical losses in the drive train, and
- find a way to coil the tether while decreasing the power consumption.

In the following chapters, the four recommendations of action are discussed. The requirements are stated, solutions generated, properties analyzed, and decisions made.

2.3.3 Performance Indicators

In this development stage, the technical aspects of the feasibility are the focus; nevertheless also the economics of the system should be considered. Performance indicators have to be introduced to be able to compare different concepts and subconcepts. These have to represent the requirements that have been described: The costs of energy have been determined as an important factor for the market success. The efficiency shall be increased

to prove the kite power system's potential. In order to use the ground station as a demonstration object, it has to be transportable and therefore volume and weight are limited. Thus the following performance indicators are used to compare the different concepts discussed in the following chapters:

- efficiency,
- costs.
- volume & weight, and
- reliability.

These performance indicators cover all properties of the concepts. The efficiency includes mechanical and electrical losses. The costs represent direct and indirect investment costs. The volume & weight are important for the transportation of the ground station. And its reliability comprises the wear of the ground station elements and on the tether along with the resulting maintenance costs during operation, including the aspect of complexity⁴⁵.

In Table 2-1, the scores are assigned to the estimation of the various properties. These values are used to compare the qualities of partial solutions in the step *properties assessment*.

Description	Score
Very good	4
Good	3
Medium	2
Bad	1

Table 2-1.: *Scores for properties assessments*

For the *decision making* the assessed properties are weighted by means of Table 2-2.

Description	Weight
Very important	9
Important	3
Less important	1

Table 2-2.: *Weighting of properties*

⁴⁵Higher complexity results in higher maintenance costs due to more frequent inspections to prevent failures.

Chapter 3 Generator Concept

In the last chapter, the electrical machine was identified as one of the key design issues for the ground station due to the fact that it causes 46% of the total energy losses; and the costs of the electrical machine and the motor controller¹ are estimated at 32% of the total material costs of the ground station [Sch11b, p. XY]. Inseparably linked to the electrical machine is the gearbox. Therefore this chapter focuses on the selection of the adequate electrical machine and gearbox, which together form the generator concept.

An electrical machine converts the rotational power of the drum into electrical power, which is fed into the grid or battery during the reel-out phase. During the reel-in phase, the same or another electrical machine provides mechanical power to retrieve the kite. If the base speed of the electrical machine rotor is significantly higher than the rotation speed of the drum, the gearbox converts the slow rotation of the drum into a fast rotation of the electrical machine - and vice versa.

To answer the proposed questions, the *munich procedure model* is used recursively. After an overview is obtained in the *goal planning*, the requirements are defined in the *goal analysis*. In the step *task structuring* the *relation function model* of the generator concept is detailed on the basis of the *relation function model* of the ground station and actions are recommended. Afterwards the three subconcepts: drive train configuration, gearbox, and electrical machine type are examined. The steps *generation of solution ideas*, *properties assessment*, and *decision making* are applied on these subconcepts. After all subconcepts are discussed, the same steps are carried out for the generator concept.

3.1 Generator Concept - Goal Planning, Goal Analysis and Task Structuring

3.1.1 Goal Planning

In the first step of the *munich procedure model*, *goal planning*, the generator concept used in the existing ground station is examined. The current ground station uses a squirrel cage induction machine, which works alternatively as a generator during the reel-out phase and as a motor during the reel-in phase. It has four poles, a nominal speed of 1,450 rpm at 50 Hz and a capacity of 18.5 kW. A 1:1 timing belt connects the drum to the gear shaft decreasing the axial length of the assembly. An epicyclic gearbox, with a transmission of 1:6.2, increases the rotation speed of the drum to the squirrel cage induction machine. No clutch is used to decouple the squirrel cage induction machine from the drum. The

¹The motor controller controls the frequency of the electrical power.

timing belt provides clearance between the drum and the gear shaft, so the connection is not completely rigid.

Figure 3-1.: *Current generator concept*

3.1.2 Goal Analysis

In this step, the requirements of the generator concept are defined. Firstly, general requirements and constraints are gathered, then the predicted load profile is examined.

The ground station shall be designed for 20 kW electrical net output power $P_{el,net}$. The Cycle Model, described in Appendix A.15, estimates the necessary average mechanical power for the reel-out at 50 kW and the average mechanical power during the reel-in phase at -20 kW (see Figure 3-2).

The nominal mechanical power during the reel-out phase $P_{mech,ro,nom}$ can be derived from the average mechanical power $P_{mech,ro,avg}$ and the mechanical crest factor² for the reel-out $C_{mech,ro}$ at 75 kW. The calculation and definitions of the performance factors are given in Appendix A.9.

The nominal wind speed $v_{W,nom}$, which is needed to achieve $P_{mech,ro,nom}$, is 9.5 m/s (see Appendix A.15 for calculation). As long as the existing 25 m² kite is used, a maximal tether force $F_{T,max}$ of 11 kN can be withstood, and a minimum tether force $F_{T,min}$ of 800 N has to be maintained for a stable flight due to the weight of the pod and to avoid

²The mechanical crest factor is defined as the ratio of nominal mechanical power and average mechanical power during reel-out.

Figure 3-2.: Predicted power output

slack tether [vdV11]. The tether that shall be used to stand this force F_T has a diameter d_T of 5 mm (see Section 4.1.3). The diameter of the drum³ d_D shall be 0.3 m for this calculation (as in the existing ground station). This is a compromise between maintaining a high diameter ratio to reduce the wear of the tether (see Appendix A.13) and a low transmission ratio which can be provided by a single-stage gearbox (see Section 3.3)⁴. The tether speeds derived from the model suggests the reel-out speed to be 25% and the reel-in speed to be -75% of the wind speed. On the basis of these assumptions, the maximum rotation speed for the reel-out $n_{D,ro,max}$ is calculated at 510 rpm, for the reel-in $n_{D,ri,max}$ at -892 rpm. The minimum and maximum torque at the drum $T_{D,min}$ and $T_{D,max}$ are calculated to 120 Nm and 1,650 Nm. The calculations can be found in Appendix A.9.

3.1.3 Task Structuring

In the step, *task structuring*, the *relation function model* developed in Chapter 2.3 is detailed. Afterwards, the design questions for the generator concept are formulated.

³In this thesis, the drum diameter is assumed to be constant. In fact it changes when the tether is coiled or uncoiled. If 20 layers of a 5 mm tether are assumed, the difference between the drum diameter at the beginning of the reel-out phase and end of the reel-out phase (the active tether length is 250 m) is smaller than 25 mm.

⁴In Chapter 5 the effect of changing the drum diameter is discussed.

Relation Function Model

The key functions of the generator concept are:

- to convert the mechanical power of the drum into electrical power during the reel-out phase and
- to convert electrical power into mechanical power during the reel-in phase.

Additionally, the optional functions “increase the rotation speed” and “decrease rotation speed” can be introduced: If the rotation of the drum shall be converted directly into electrical power by an electrical machine, the number of poles must be higher (see Section 3.3). Therefore these functions have been added. In Figure A-19 in Appendix A.7.4, the key functions and directly attached functions are shown.

The conversion of mechanical into electrical power requires a prior conversion of the translational movement of the tether into the rotational movement of the drum. Also the ability to measure and control the input and output parameters (torque, rotation speed, current, voltage, and frequency) is necessary. The desired subsequent functions are the storage of electrical energy and the supply of electrical power for auxiliaries (e. g. control stand and sensors). The conversion of electrical into mechanical power requires an electrical power supply. The mechanical power is converted into translational power to reel-in the kite. In both conversions electrical losses are inevitable (adverse function).

Recommended Actions

Three design questions arise from the previous section, which together form the generator concept:

- Which drive train configuration shall be used?
- Which gearbox concept shall be used?
- Which type of electrical machine shall be used?

These questions are treated in the next sections in succession. For every subconcept, the steps *generation of solution ideas*, *properties assessment*, and *decision making* are carried out. After these design questions have been answered, the (overall) generator concepts are developed as a synthesis of the subconcepts.

3.2 Drive Train Configuration

The drive train configuration addresses two questions: Shall one or two electrical machines be used, and how shall they be coupled to the drum?

3.2.1 Generation of Solution Ideas

The two functions of converting mechanical into electrical power and vice versa can be either fulfilled by one electrical machine operating in turn as generator and motor, or two distinct electrical machines; one of them always operating as a generator and the other as a motor. The electrical machine(s) can either be coupled rigidly to the drum via shafts and gears, or a clutch can be integrated to couple and decouple the electrical machine shaft(s) from the drum shaft.

If the two functions are integrated into one electrical machine, this electrical machine has to change the rotation direction between the reel-in and reel-out phase. Two configurations with one electrical machine are possible:

- The electrical machine is rigidly connected to the drum: rigidly connected electrical machine concept (REM).
- The electrical machine is coupled with a clutch to the drum: clutch coupled electrical machine concept (CEM).

If two distinct machines are used, four configurations are possible:

- The generator and motor are rigidly connected to the drum shaft: rigidly connected generator and motor concept (RGRM)
- The generator is connected rigidly to the shaft of the drum, while the motor is connected with a clutch which can be mechanically coupled and decoupled: rigidly connected generator and clutch coupled motor concept (RGCM).
- The generator is connected with a clutch which can be mechanically coupled and decoupled, while the motor is connected rigidly to the shaft of the drum: clutch coupled generator and rigidly connected motor concept (CGRM).
- Both, the generator and motor, can be mechanically decoupled: clutch coupled generator and motor concept (CGCM).

In Figure 3-3 these six concepts are shown.

For control and safety reasons, all rotational parts must be able to be braked (as in hoisting applications [PNP04, p. 16]). Thus depending on the concept chosen, one to three brakes have to be integrated. The six possibilities given above are discussed in the next sections.

Figure 3-3.: Overview of drive train concepts

3.2.2 Properties Assessment

The performance indicators of Section 2.3.3 are used to assess the properties of the different drive train configurations in the following paragraphs: efficiency, costs, volume & weight, and reliability.

To evaluate the configurations, the performance indicators are pairwise compared to the most similar configuration since this points out best the differences between them. Afterwards these *pairwise comparisons* are assembled and a decision matrix is calculated. The following *pairwise comparisons* have been carried out:

- the REM is used as reference,
- the CEM and RGRM are compared to the REM,
- the RGCM and CGRM are compared to the RGRM, and
- the CGCM is compared to the CGRM.

At the end of every comparison, a table evaluates the performance indicators with scores, where the given concept is evaluated relatively to its reference.

Description	Score
Significantly better	2
Slightly better	1
Approximately equal	0
Slightly worse	-1
Significantly worse	-2

Table 3-1.: Scores for pairwise comparison

One machine rigidly connected to the drum (Relectrical machine)

If the electrical machine with a nominal capacity of 50 kW is rigidly connected to the drum (geared or direct-driven)⁵, the rotor has to change its direction according to the cycle phase. The efficiencies of the electrical machine for generator and motor mode are dependent on the rotation speed and torque. During generation, the rotation speed is lower and the torque is higher than in motor mode, therefore a compromise must be found to optimize the electrical efficiency over the cycle. One brake is needed to decelerate the drive train.

Figure 3-4.: *REM drive train concept*

In Figure 3-4, the scheme of the REM is shown.

One machine coupled with a clutch to the drum (CEM)

If the electrical machine can be coupled and decoupled, it is possible to accelerate and decelerate the rotor independently from the drum and vice versa. The clutch prevents overload passively: When the tether force exceeds a certain (adjustable) value, the clutch slips and causes the tether speed to increase. A second brake is necessary to brake the drum and the (decoupled) electrical machine. The two brakes prevent a standstill of the electrical machine rotor, thus protecting the bearings, by coupling the slow turning rotor gradually to the drum turning in the opposite direction⁶. The efficiency is slightly lower when compared to the REM, since losses in the clutch appear and power for the additional brake has to be provided. The additional elements increase the costs and the volume & weight of the CEM slightly. The reliability of the concept is slightly higher than the REM due to the overload protection of the clutch, which compensates short wind gusts and the decreased wear of the bearings.

In Figure 3-5, the scheme of the CEM is shown. Table 3-2 summarizes the comparison.

⁵The integration of a gearbox is discussed in Section 3.3.

⁶The wear of bearings when they are moved from the standstill are much higher than when they are in movement [Jas11].

Figure 3-5.: *CEM drive train concept*

Properties	CEM vs. REM	Score
Efficiency	Slightly lower	-1
Costs	Slightly higher	-1
Volume & weight	Slightly higher	-1
Reliability	Slightly higher	1

Table 3-2.: *Properties of the CEM in comparison to the REM configuration*

Two machines, both rigidly connected to the drum (RGRM)

If both electrical machines, with capacities of 50 kW and 20 kW, are rigidly connected to the drum, the generator rotor must still be designed for the higher rotation speeds of the reel-in phase. It is not reasonable to use both electrical machines in generator and motor mode, since then the RGRM does not have any advantage over the REM: The efficiency decreases with smaller size and more bearings; the costs of two electrical machine, with the same capacity as a single one, are higher; the volume & weight increase; and the reliability decreases because of more elements. The only possible advantage could be that a back up is present in case control is lost over one electrical machine. A valid possibility to implement the RGRM is the electrical decoupling of both electrical machines.

An electrical machine is electrically decoupled when either the stator connection to the motor controller is interrupted or the rotor is disconnected from its excitation⁷.

If the electrical machines are electrically decoupled, the generator rotor represents an additional inertia during the reel-in phase and the motor rotor during the reel-out phase thus degrading the dynamic of the drive train.

The efficiency is positively affected by the fact that both electrical machines can be optimized for the relevant phase; but on the other hand, the additional inertia and friction have a negative influence. It is assumed that the efficiency is approximately equal to the REM⁸.

⁷Permanent magnet synchronous machine cannot be used, because the magnetic field cannot be varied.

⁸To weigh both effects against each other, a quantitative analysis of the inertias and efficiencies would be required which is beyond the focus of this thesis.

The use of a second electrical machine increases the costs substantially and also heighten the volume & weight.

The use of two electrical machines can be seen as a back up system, if one electrical machine fails. In contrast to this, the reliability decreases with the use of more elements. It is assumed that the RGRM reliability is comparable to the REM⁹.

Figure 3-6.: *RGRM drive train concept*

In Figure 3-6, the scheme of the RGRM is shown. Table 3-3 summarizes the results of the comparison.

Properties	RGRM vs. REM	Score
Efficiency	Approximately equal	0
Costs	Substantially higher	-2
Volume & Weight	Substantially higher	-2
Reliability	Approximately equal	0

Table 3-3.: *Properties of the RGRM in comparison to the REM configuration*

Two machines, the generator rigidly connected and the motor coupled with a clutch to the drum (RGCM)

The generator rotor has to be designed for the reel-in speeds and be electrically decoupleable (compare to RGRM). The motor can maintain its direction of rotation and must not be reversed. A second brake for the motor shaft and a clutch must be integrated.

The clutch and additional brake cause some losses; on the other hand, the motor is decoupled during the reel-out phase and decreases the inertia and friction. The efficiency is assumed to be comparable to the RGRM.

The costs and the volume & weight are slightly higher.

The reliability is slightly lower than in the RGRM, since there is no obvious advantage if the motor can be decoupled but more elements present more potential failures.

⁹Again, the number of failures, prevented by a back up, compared to the additional effort for maintenance, must be assessed quantitatively to make a nonambiguous statement.

Figure 3-7.: *RGCM drive train concept*

In Figure 3-7 the scheme of the RGCM is shown. In Table 3-4 the assessed properties are summarized.

Properties	RGCM vs. RGRM	Score
Efficiency	Approximately equal	0
Costs	Slightly higher	-1
Volume & Weight	Slightly higher	-1
Reliability	Approximately equal	0

Table 3-4.: *Properties of the RGCM in comparison to the RGRM configuration*

Two machines, the generator coupled with a clutch and the motor rigidly connected to the drum (CGRM)

In this configuration the nominal capacity of the generator can be decreased to 40 kW because the motor can assume a part of the load during the reel-out phase¹⁰. During the reel-out phase the generator is coupled and both electrical machines are in operation. During the reel-in phase, the generator is disconnected and the motor drives the drum. The generator either stands still or is moved with low speed to omit the initial friction when started, so it does not have to change direction. This increases the efficiency in comparison to the RGRM.

The generator is smaller than in the RGRM, but an additional clutch and brake are needed. The costs and volume & weight are therefore assumed to be approximately equal.

The effect of having more elements and the protection needed against overload during the reel-out are assumed to neutralize each other. So, the reliability is as high as in the RGRM configuration.

In Figure 3-8 the scheme of the CGRM is shown. In Table 3-5 the results of the *pairwise comparison* are compiled.

¹⁰It is assumed that the motor can provide at least 50% of its nominal torque when it is driven with 50% of the nominal rotation speed [Alx10a]

Figure 3-8.: *CGRM drive train concept*

Properties	CGRM vs. RGRM	Score
Efficiency	Higher	1
Costs	Approximately equal	0
Volume & Weight	Approximately equal	0
Reliability	Approximately equal	0

Table 3-5.: *Properties of the CGRM in comparison to the RGRM configuration*

Two machines, both coupled to the drum with a clutch (CGCM)

In this configuration, the generator has a capacity of 50 kW and the motor of 20 kW. The generator is only connected during the reel-out phase and the motor only during the reel-in phase. Thus, the rotation of both electrical machines do not have to change.

The efficiency is significantly increased compared to the CGRM, since the direction of the rotor of the motor does not have to be changed and generally the efficiency of one bigger electrical machine is higher than of two electrical machines with the same capacity [Ele].

The costs of the CGCM are higher than those of the CGRM, since one additional clutch and one brake are needed and the generator capacity is increased in the CGCM concept. The volume & weight of the concept are also slightly higher, for the same reasons.

The reliability is assumed to be higher, since the decreased wear of both machines is estimated to have a higher influence than the increased maintenance and possibility of failures of the additional elements.

Figure 3-9.: *CGCM drive train concept*

In Figure 3-9, the scheme of the CGCM is shown. In Table 3-6, the relative scores for the comparison are displayed.

Properties	CGCM vs. CGRM	Score
Efficiency	Significantly increased	2
Costs	Higher	-1
Volume & Weight	Higher	-1
Reliability	Higher	1

Table 3-6.: *Properties of the CGCM in comparison to the CGRM configuration*

3.2.3 Decision Making

In Table 3-7, the results of the *pairwise comparisons* are summarized¹¹.

Properties	REM	CEM	RGRM	RGCM	CGRM	CGCM
Efficiency	0	-1	0	0	1	3
Costs	0	-1	-2	-3	-2	-3
Volume & Weight	0	-1	-2	-3	-2	-3
Reliability	0	1	0	0	0	1

Table 3-7.: *Synthesis of the pairwise comparisons*

The REM has been used as reference and scores therefore in every category. The RGRM and RGCM do not score better than the REM in any category. The CEM has a slight advantage in reliability and the CGRM has a better efficiency than the REM. Only the CGCM scores better than the reference REM in two categories: in efficiency and in reliability, but it lags behind in costs and volume & weight.

The relative scores are transferred into the scores in Table 3-8 as proposed in Section 2.3.3.

Configuration	Efficiency	Costs	Volume & Weight	Reliability
REM	2	4	4	2
CEM	1	4	4	3
RGRM	2	3	2	2
RGCM	2	2	2	2
CGRM	3	3	3	2
CGCM	4	2	2	3

Table 3-8.: *Properties of drive train configurations*

¹¹The values in Table 3-7 are obtained by means of addition of the relative scores of the *pairwise comparison*

These properties are now weighted according to Table 3-9. In the selection of electrical machines the focus lies on efficiency and costs. The total efficiency of the ground station is proportional to the electrical machine efficiency, therefore this has quite a strong effect on the energy yield of the kite power system. The costs of the electrical machine are a substantial part of the total costs of the ground station, therefore they have a significant influence on the total investment costs. The volume & weight are restricted by the constraints of the trailer and car, but within these limits they do not present critical properties. The reliability of the electrical machine is also not weighted especially strong, since other elements of the kite power system (for instance the tether) have a much shorter life time and the differences of the various concepts are expected to be rather small.

Properties	Weight
Efficiency	9
Costs	9
Volume & weight	3
Reliability	3

Table 3-9.: *Weighting of drive train properties*

The multiplication of the property matrix and the weighting matrix results in a decision matrix presented in Table 3-10. The weighted properties are summed up and the ranks of the configurations are given¹².

Configuration	Eff.	Costs	Vol. & weight	Rel.	Sum	Rank
REM	18	36	12	6	72	1
CEM	9	36	12	9	66	4
RGRM	18	27	6	6	57	5
RGCM	18	18	6	6	48	6
CGRM	27	27	9	6	69	2
CGCM	36	18	6	9	69	2

Table 3-10.: *Decision matrix for drive train configuration*

It is recommended to use either the REM or the CGCM concept. The REM concept is probably the least expensive, smallest, and lightest. The CGCM on the other side is assumed to be the most efficient. The CGRM scores equally with the CGCM but has been eliminated due to the more complex control for the combined generation of the electrical machines.

In the synthesis, the REM and CGCM configuration are assembled with the gearbox concept and the type of the electrical machine(s) which are examined in the following sections.

¹²It is highly recommended to be critical about results of such calculations, especially when different options are evaluated subjectively, like here.

3.3 Gearbox Concept

3.3.1 Goal Analysis

In Chapter 3.1.2, the nominal reel-out speed $v_{T,ro,nom}$ was assumed to be 6.7 m/s, which corresponds with a rotational speed of the drum $n_{D,ro,nom}$ of 427 rpm when the drum diameter d_D is assumed to be constant at 0.3 m (see Appendix A.9 for calculation). The rotation speed of the drum during reel-in $n_{D,ri,nom}$ is derived from the nominal reel-in speed $v_{T,ri,nom}$ of -7.1 m/s, to -452 rpm. The grid frequency f_{Grid} is 50 Hz. The number of poles¹³ in the rotor p defines the rotation speed of the generator n_{gen} which is necessary to obtain this frequency. The electrical power output of an electrical machine is approximately proportional to its rotation speed [Alx10b]. Therefore the transmission ratio i of the gearbox must be adapted to the electrical machine. The highest transmission ratio is necessary if a two-pole electrical machine is used. In Table 3-11, the transmission ratios for the nominal drum speed at a wind speed of 9.5 m/s are shown¹⁴.

Number of poles	Base speed (rpm)	Maximal speed (rpm)	$i_{ri,max}$	$i_{ro,max}$
2	3000	5700	6.39	11.18
4	1500	2850	3.20	5.59
6	1000	1900	2.13	3.73
8	750	1425	1.60	2.79
10	600	1140	1.28	2.24
12	500	950	1.07	1.86
14	429	815.1	0.91	1.60
16	375	712.5	0.80	1.40

Table 3-11.: *Dependency of the base speed of the number of poles and the resulting transmission ratios for reel-in and reel-out*

Gearboxes are designed for a certain torque and rotation speed. Due to the different working points in reel-out and reel-in phases, this results in a lower efficiency of the gearbox if only one electrical machine is used.

3.3.2 Generation of Solution Ideas

Three types of gearboxes are considered: a mechanical gearbox, a magnetic gearbox, and a direct-drive concept which omits the gearbox¹⁵.

¹³In literature p sometimes stands also for the number of pole pairs

¹⁴It is assumed for now, that the new motor controller is capable of a maximal frequency f_{max} of 95 Hz as the current one.[Fec11b] It has to be kept in mind that the rotor of the electrical machine has to be able to achieve this rotation speed without failure. The bigger the electrical machine is, the bigger the inertia of the rotor and the centripetal forces are that act on the structure.

¹⁵Hydraulic gearboxes have not been considered since they require a hydraulic circle, and an evaluation of such a system was beyond the focus of this thesis.

3.3.3 Properties Assessment

The properties analysed are: efficiency, costs, volume & weight, reliability (see Section 2.3.3) and additionally the gear ratio. The gear ratio determines the number of stages that is necessary to increase the rotation speed. The evaluation of this criterion is linked to the gear ratios that are necessary for the reel-out and reel-in phases.

Gear ratio	Score
> 11	4
> 6	3
> 3	2
< 3	1

Table 3-12.: Scores for achievable gear ratios

Mechanical Gearbox

The efficiency model¹⁶ for the gearbox was determined by the friction test that was carried out at the Technical University of Delft (see Figure 3-10).

Figure 3-10.: Gearbox efficiency according to model derived from friction test [Fec11c]

The efficiency for the nominal values of the reel-out phase is 97.0% and for the reel-in phase 87.7%¹⁷. The volume & weight for epicyclic gears is relatively low [Sch10, p. 778]. The main failure of (large) wind turbines is the gearbox [Jas11]. The reliability is therefore assumed medium. The maximum gear ratio of an epicyclic gear stage is 1:10 [Sch10, p. 774].

¹⁶The model is on basis of a static friction of 122 N and a dynamic friction of $30.6 \frac{N}{m/s}$.

¹⁷Models used for wind turbines calculate with a loss of 1% per stage. [PVDT06, p. 3]. This is not applicable to the kite power system since the dimensions of wind turbines are significantly larger.

Magnetic Gearing

Some of the disadvantages of mechanical gearboxes, such as contact friction, noise, and heat [GMBR11, p. 1], have awoken interest in recent research in meagnetic gearings [ACH04], [ATM08], [RACH10], [GMBR11]. In Figure 3-11, a scheme of such a magnetic gear is shown [GMBR11, p. 7].

Figure 3-11.: Scheme of a magnetic gear [GMBR11, p. 7]

The maximal ratio of such a magnetic gearbox can be as high as 1:11 [ACH04, p. 3]. The efficiency of a magnetic gear is shown in Figure 3-12 [ACH04, p. 8]¹⁸.

Figure 3-12.: Efficiency of a magnetic gear with a gear ratio of 5.75:1 [ACH04, p. 8]

In comparison to the mechanical gear stage, the efficiency is slightly higher, but it has to be kept in mind that the transmittable torque of the magnetic and mechanical gearings are different, therefore caution is appropriate. Especially, since it seems that no magnetic gearing in the required dimension is available on the market influences.

¹⁸In newer literature no efficiencies were mentioned.

Direct-drive

The direct-drive concept omits the gearbox. The number of rotor poles in the electrical machine have to be increased to achieve the grid frequency (see above). This leads to a high efficiency and reliability, both advantages, but large size, high weight and high costs of the generator are all disadvantages [PBLC11, p. 12].

Property Overview

The analyzed properties are summarized in Table 3-13.

Gearbox	Eff.	Costs	Vol. & weight	Rel.	Max. transm.
Mechanical	2	4	3	2	3
Magnetic	3	1	3	4	4
Direct-drive	4	2	2	4	1

Table 3-13.: *Properties of gearbox concepts*

Efficiency is highest for the direct-drive concept, the costs are lowest for the mechanical gearbox due to the increase of costs for electrical machines with increasing torque and the same power rating (see Appendix A.16).

3.3.4 Decision Making

The properties are weighted in Table 3-14. The efficiency and costs considered the most important properties. The reliability is of lesser importance.

Property	Weighting
Efficiency	9
Costs	9
Volume & weight	3
Reliability	1
Transmission ratio	3

Table 3-14.: *Weighting of gearbox properties*

The matrices of Table 3-13 and Table 3-14 are multiplied to calculate the decision matrix in Table 3-15.

The magnetic gearbox is eliminated due its uncertain properties and the state of research. A mechanical gearbox should only be used when two distinct electrical machines for reel-in and reel-out phases are used, since the efficiency is significantly reduced for the reel-in phase. For a configuration with only one electrical machine, the direct-drive concept is preferred. The use of gearboxes in the two electrical machine configurations has advantages

Gearbox	Eff.	Costs	Vol. & weight	Rel.	Max. transm.	Sum	Rank
Mechanical	18	36	9	2	9	74	1
Magnetic	27	9	9	4	12	61	3
Direct-drive	36	18	6	4	3	67	2

Table 3-15.: *Decision matrix for gearbox concepts*

in costs and volume & weight, on the other hand, the omittance of the gearbox increases efficiency and reliability.

3.4 Electrical Machine Type

3.4.1 Generation of Solution Ideas

The different types of electrical machines are shown in Figure A-22 in Appendix A.10 as a hierarchical tree. Linear electrical machines and stepper electrical machines are not further considered since they do not fit into the continuous rotation movement of the drum. Even if the energy is stored in a battery, a grid connection shall be possible, therefore only three-phase alternating current (AC) is examined¹⁹. The switched reluctance machine is excluded due to its lower efficiency and lower power factor in comparison to the induction machine. The solid rotor of the induction machine is also excluded due to its worse efficiency in comparison to other types. Thus the induction machine and the synchronous machine are considered as possibilities. Induction machines have either wound (singly-fed or doubly-fed) rotors or squirrel cage rotors. The synchronous machine can be further differentiated in rotors with permanent magnets and electrically excited rotors.

In the following paragraphs, the principles of induction machines and synchronous machines are described and the different types detailed. Afterwards, the properties of these types are compared to each other in regard to the same criteria as the drive train concepts: efficiency (taking into account the speed range of the electrical machine), costs (including the costs of the motor controller), volume & weight, and reliability.

¹⁹Direct current (DC) machines are not common in the desired power rating [Hug09, p. 367] and are not used anymore since motor controllers nowadays enable AC electrical machines to outclass DC electrical machines [Ige11].

3.4.2 Properties Assessment

Induction Machine - General

The induction machine operates as a motor if the magnetic field of the stator rotates faster than the rotor, and as a generator, if the rotor driven by the prime mover turns faster than the synchronous speed n_s . Induction machines always draw reactive power from the grid²⁰ [Fec11b]. The resulting curve of the torque T over rotation speed n is shown in Figure 3-13²¹. Three different operation modes can be distinguished depending on the shaft speed: the motor mode ($0 < n < n_s$), the generator mode ($n > n_s$), and the braking mode ($n < 0$).

Figure 3-13.: *Torque-speed characteristics of an induction machine*

Induction motors are often used in industrial drives due to their robustness and low costs when compared to synchronous motors [Par03, p. 1]. Induction generators are used in wind turbines due to their robustness, mechanical simplicity, and low price in comparison to the synchronous generators [KDK06, p. 1]. The induction machines that are described in more detail are the SCIM, the wound rotor induction machine, and doubly-fed wound rotor induction machine²².

Squirrel Cage Induction Machine

The squirrel cage induction machine is the most common type for industry motors, representing 90% of all induction motors [PNP04, p. 2]. It has its name due to its similarity

²⁰In case of the kite power system they draw the reactive power from the motor controller which needs a higher power rating and is therefore more expensive.

²¹The slip s is also displayed.

²²In literature about wind turbines, the term “generator” instead of “machine” is used. The electrical machine types are therefore abbreviated as “SCIG”, “WRIG”, and “DFIG”.

with the rotor form and a hamster wheel (see Figure 3-14).

Figure 3-14.: *Squirrel cage rotor [PNP04, p. 2]*

It can be used as a generator in fixed speed wind turbines with a multiple-stage gearbox without a converter. A capacitor can be integrated to compensate the reactive power drawn from the grid [LC08, p. 2]. If a converter with a 120% power rating (on the basis of the generator power rating) is added, variable speed operation is possible [PBLC11, p. 11]. Figure 3-15 shows the scheme of a wind turbine with a squirrel cage induction machine for variable speed operation.

Figure 3-15.: *Scheme of a wind turbine with an SCIM [LC08, p. 2]*

Wound Rotor Induction Machine

The wound rotor induction machine is used in limited variable speed²³ wind turbines with a multiple-stage gearbox - also known as the “Optislip Concept” - which has a range of about 10% above the base speed [LC08, p. 125]. While the stator is the same as in the squirrel cage induction machine, the windings on the rotor are not short-circuited but separately connected to slip rings (see Figure 3-16) [PNP04, p. 7]. It is possible - by increasing an additional resistance to the rotor - to obtain a high torque at low rotation speed [PNP04, p. 6]. Figure 3-17 shows the scheme of a wind turbine with a wound rotor induction machine.

Doubly-fed Induction Machine

In the doubly-fed wound rotor induction machine, the stator has a direct connection to the grid as in the configurations above. The rotor is (in contrast to the other induction

²³Limited variable speed turbines have a certain speed range in which they can operate.

Figure 3-17.: *Scheme of a wind turbine with an WRIM*

machine configurations) also connected to the grid through a converter, feeding-in a part of the electrical power. With this configuration, a variable speed of $\pm 30\%$ around the synchronous speed is possible. The rating of the power converter is 30% of the generator power rating due to the fact that only a part of the power is processed in the converter, while the main part is fed directly into the grid [LC08, p. 126] [PBLC11, p. 11]. In Figure 3-18 such a DFIM configuration is shown.

Figure 3-18.: *Scheme of a wind turbine with an DFIM*

Synchronous Machine - General

The synchronous machine uses the effect of induction in the rotor due to a changing magnetic field. The stator is similar to the induction machine, while the rotor is either electrical excited or consists of permanent magnets. In Figure 3-19, the torque-speed characteristic of a synchronous machine is shown. The synchronous machine needs a full-scale converter whether it is an electrical excited synchronous machine or a permanent magnet synchronous machine to enable speed variations.

One important ability is the possibility of operating the synchronous machine with:

- lagging power factor ($PF < 1$, $\phi > 0$: current behind voltage),

Figure 3-19.: *Torque-speed characteristic of a synchronous machine with flux weakening [Pol10]*

- unity power factor ($\text{PF} = 1$, $\phi = 0$: current and voltage in same phase), or
- leading power factor ($\text{PF} < 1$, $\phi < 0$: current leads voltage).

This degree of freedom enables the reduction of reactive power losses [Fec11b]. Synchronous generators are used primarily in power plants (up to 1 GW) for the - above mentioned - ability of reducing reactive power losses. Synchronous motors are used in large (> 1 MW) constant or low speed drives [Pol10, 29.9.2010, s. 28].

Electrically Excited Synchronous Machine

The rotor of an electrical excited synchronous machine is excited with direct current (DC) using slip rings (brushed) or a rotating rectifier (brushless) and can be built as salient poles (mostly used for lower rotation speeds) or cylindrically. The generator speed can be controlled over a wide range by flux weakening or frequency control [Pol10, 04.10.2010, s. 15 ff.] to minimize losses in different power ranges. This configuration is used in most direct-drive wind turbines [PBLC11, p. 13].

Permanent Magnet Synchronous Machine

The permanent magnet synchronous machine integrates permanent magnets in the rotor instead of coils to omit its electrical excitation. Several topologies are common with regard to the air gap orientation, stator core orientation, magnet orientation and copper housing [Dub04, p. 14].

Two problems may occur with permanent magnet synchronous machine: The magnets demagnetize at high temperature [PBLC11, p. 14] and they corrode in salt water [Pol11].

Properties Comparison

The properties of the different electrical machine types are compiled relatively to each other. The *efficiency* of the electrical machine must take the load profile of the kite power system into account, since in every cycle the rotation speed and the torque vary highly. According to [PBL11, p. 14], the nominal efficiency of the permanent magnet synchronous machine is higher than that of the electrical excited synchronous machine. The electrical excited synchronous machine, on the other hand, has the advantage that the speed is controllable over the entire operation range [PBL11, p. 13]. It is assumed that the permanent magnet synchronous machine has a higher efficiency than the electrical excited synchronous machine. The efficiency of the squirrel cage induction machine is compared in [PBL11, p. 38] to the permanent magnet synchronous machine. Under nominal load, the efficiency of the squirrel cage induction machine is higher than the efficiency under nominal load of the permanent magnet synchronous machine²⁴. But the average efficiency of the squirrel cage induction machine is slightly lower than that of the permanent magnet synchronous machine. It is assumed that this results from a higher efficiency over the speed range²⁵. The wound rotor induction machine has a lower efficiency than the squirrel cage induction machine due to the fact that an external resistor dissipates power to enable variable speed operation [LC08, p. 3]. The doubly-fed wound rotor induction machine has according to [PVDT06, p. 5] a slightly lower efficiency than the permanent magnet synchronous machine.

The *costs* of the permanent magnet synchronous machine are estimated to be lower than the costs of the electrical excited synchronous machine and the doubly-fed wound rotor induction machine [PVDT06, p. 5]²⁶. The squirrel cage induction machine is probably the most economical option because it is the most common one used in industry. The wound rotor induction machine has a layout similar to the doubly-fed wound rotor induction machine without the second connection, therefore its costs are assumed to lie somewhere between the squirrel cage induction machine and the doubly-fed wound rotor induction machine.

The *volume & weight* of the permanent magnet synchronous machine is significantly lower than that of the doubly-fed wound rotor induction machine. The volume & weight of the electrical excited synchronous machine is assumed as high as that of the doubly-fed wound rotor induction machine [PVDT06, p. 5]. The volume & weight of the squirrel cage induction machine and wound rotor induction machine is assumed to be slightly smaller than that of the doubly-fed wound rotor induction machine due to the omission

²⁴Even if the losses of a gearbox are included in the comparison.

²⁵This is in contrast to the statement, that the efficiency of squirrel cage induction machines are in relation to synchronous machines is lower at the nominal working point, but do not decrease so fast if the electrical machine is operated at other working points [Ige11]. This contradiction has to be solved.

²⁶The costs of rare earth metals vary strongly. Therefore it is questionable if a reliable statement can be made about the costs of permanent magnet synchronous machine. In [PBL11, p. 14] the costs are considered a disadvantage of the permanent magnet synchronous machine.

of the second connection from the rotor to the grid or energy storage and otherwise similar design.

The *reliability* of the squirrel cage induction machine is high since no slip rings are used. The wound rotor induction machine and doubly-fed wound rotor induction machine use slip rings and their reliability is therefore evaluated lower. The permanent magnet synchronous machine has also high reliability because no excitation is needed. The reliability of the electrical excited synchronous machine is assumed to be slightly lower than the one of the permanent magnet synchronous machine.

The assessed properties are compiled in Table 3-16 by means of the score table in Section 2.3.3.

	Efficiency	Costs	Volume & weight	Reliability
SCIM	2	4	3	4
WRIM	1	3	3	2
DFIM	3	1	2	2
EESM	3	1	2	3
PMSM	4	2	4	4

Table 3-16.: *Properties of electrical machine types*

3.4.3 Decision Making

The assessed properties in the last section build the basis on which the decision for the type(s) is made. The properties are weighted in Table 3-17. The efficiency is evaluated as most the important factor since the focus of the new ground station is to improve the total efficiency, which is proportional to the electrical machine efficiency. The costs are taken into account with medium importance since they represent a significant share of the total material costs of the ground station. The other performance factors are less important: The volume & weight do not affect the choice unless the maximum weight for the trailer is exceeded, and the differences in reliability are not expected to be significant in comparison to other ground station elements.

Properties	Weight
Efficiency	9
Costs	3
Volume & weight	1
Reliability	1

Table 3-17.: *Weighting of properties of electrical machine types*

The multiplication of the properties evaluation and the properties weighting is given in the decision matrix in Table 3-18

	Efficiency	Costs	Volume & weight	Reliability	Sum	Rank
SCIM	18	12	3	4	37	2
WRIM	9	9	3	2	23	5
DFIM	27	3	2	2	34	4
EESM	27	3	2	3	35	3
PMSM	36	6	4	4	50	1

Table 3-18.: *Decision matrix for electrical machine types*

The wound rotor induction machine is inferior to the squirrel cage induction machine in every category; the electrical excited synchronous machine and doubly-fed wound rotor induction machine are eliminated since they do not have any obvious advantages over the permanent magnet synchronous machine. Therefore only the squirrel cage induction machine and permanent magnet synchronous machine are considered for the generator concept.

It has to be mentioned that the assessed properties have to be handled carefully, since the reviewed sources focus on concepts for wind turbines. For a better comparison of the properties of electrical machine types, information has to be gathered from manufacturers of electrical machines and the different types have to be modelled and perhaps even tested (see Chapter 7).

3.5 Generator Concept - Generation of Solution Ideas, Properties Assessment and Decision Making

3.5.1 Generation of Solution Ideas

The three subconcepts: drive train configuration, gearbox concept, and type of the electrical machine have been examined in the sections above. Their properties have been assessed and the most viable solutions have been pointed out. In this section, these partial solutions are brought together for the (overall) generator concept. Therefore Table 3-19 shows the *morphologic box* consisting of the partial concepts on the left side and the possible partial solutions on the right side.

Partial concepts	Partial solutions	
EM concept	REM	CGCM
Gearbox concept	Mechanical	Direct-drive
Type	SCIM	PMSM

Table 3-19.: *Morphologic box for generator concepts*

Theoretically, it is possible to combine each of the partial solutions for one partial concept with each of the others. This results in 20 possible generator concepts²⁷. Instead of carrying out a comparison for all these concepts, the number of concepts is reduced to 14 by means of compatibility matrices in which unfavorable combinations are eliminated (see Appendix A.11) [PL11, p. 121]. Additionally, the CGCM is divided into the generator and the motor side which are independent of each other. This results in 9 solutions shown in Table 3-20 for which the properties are assessed in the next section.

Solution	Drive train	Gearbox	Type
1	REM	Direct-drive	SCIM
2	REM	Direct-drive	PMSM
3	CG	Mechanical	SCIM
4	CG	Mechanical	PMSM
5	CG	Direct-drive	PMSM
6	CM	Mechanical	SCIM
7	CM	Mechanical	PMSM
8	CM	Direct-drive	SCIM
9	CM	Direct-drive	PMSM

Table 3-20.: *Solutions for the generator concept*

3.5.2 Properties Assessment

The analysis of the properties of the generator concept is exemplarily performed for squirrel cage induction machines from Marelli Motors²⁸, permanent magnet synchronous machines from Alxion²⁹, and gearboxes from Neugart³⁰.

The rated power for the electrical machine (in the REM configuration) and the generator (for the CGCM configuration) is 50 kW; the rated power for the motor in the CGCM configuration is 20 kW (see Section 3.2.2). In Appendix A.16, the properties of the electrical machines and gearboxes are listed.

The properties: efficiency³¹, weight, and costs for the generator concepts are listed³² in Table 3-21³³.

²⁷4 REM configurations and 16 CGCM configurations.

²⁸Marelli motors is an Italian producer of electrical machine.

²⁹Alxion is a French producer of direct-drive electrical machine.

³⁰Neugart is a German producer of epicyclic gearboxes.

³¹It must be aware that the nominal efficiencies from data sheets are used here. This means that the efficiencies are lower due to the dynamic operation of the kite power system - especially for the electrical machines which are operated at the reel-out and reel-in phase.

³²The dimensions of the Alxion electrical machine are not listed in the datasheets, therefore the volume is not considered. The reliability is left out since it is not assessable.

³³The electrical machines of the concepts 1 and 6 and 2 and 7 are identical but are kept since they are used in different drive train configurations.

Number	EM	Gearbox	Eff. (%)	Weight (kg)	Costs (Euro)
1	FKI 315 S8	None	93	459	4,890
2	FKI B4C 315 MA10	None	92	735	6,159
3	FKI 250 M2	PLN 190-i=4	91.14	255.5	2,174
4	FKI 250 M4	PLN 190-i=5	90.16	294.5	2,956
5	Alxion 800STK4M	None	94	138	16,400
6	FKI 315 S8	None	93	459	4,890
7	B4C 315 MA10	None	92	735	6,159
8	315 MC12	None	92	815	6,868
9	Alxion 500STK2M	None	91	43	4,500
10	FKI 200 LB6	None	89.4	145	1,302
11	FKI 225 M8	None	88.9	220	1,903
12	FKI 180 M2	PLN 142-i=3	89.0	114	1,683

Table 3-21.: *Properties of generator concept configurations*

Note that no configuration of a permanent magnet synchronous machine with a gearbox is within the solution space. This results from the slow rotation speeds of the examined permanent magnet synchronous machines and the fact that the gearboxes do not offer a smaller transmission than 1:3.

3.5.3 Decision Making

As mentioned previously, the mass of the ground station is limited to 2,800 kg. Taking into account the masses for the other elements, the weight of the electrical machine(s) and gearbox(es) have not to exceed 700 kg. Therefore the solutions 2, 7 and 8 are eliminated because their weight is too high.

From the remaining solutions four concepts are assembled: One REM with a squirrel cage induction machine without gearbox and three CGCM concepts (one with direct-driven permanent magnet synchronous machines, one with direct-driven squirrel cage induction machines and one with geared squirrel cage induction machines). In Table 3-22, the properties are drawn together.

Number(s)	Configuration	Eff. (%)	Weight (kg)	Costs (Euro)
1	REM DD SCIM	93	459	4,890
5+9	CG DD PMSM & CM DD PMSM	92.5	181	20,900
6+10	CG DD SCIM & CM DD SCIM	91.2	604	6,192
3+12	CG MECH SCIM & CM MECH SCIM	90.062	369.5	3,857

Table 3-22.: *Generator concept alternatives*

From this comparison, the first two generator concepts seem to be the most promising ones: The first has the highest efficiency, the second is the lightest. A modeling of the concepts is necessary to determine the most optimal one (see Chapter 7).

Chapter 4 Tether Guidance

After discussing the generator concept in the last chapter, the second important element, the tether guidance, is examined. The steps *goal planning*, *task structuring*, and *goal analysis*¹ are carried out for the tether guidance as a whole. Then the subordinated elements (drum, fairlead, swivel, and pulley) are handled one by one. The step, *generation of solution ideas*, *properties assessment*, and *decision making*, are carried out for each of them. After all elements have been discussed, overall concepts are compiled by means of a morphologic box. From all possible concepts, four concepts are chosen to be compared to each other. At the end of this chapter, the following design questions regarding the tether guidance are answered:

- How does the tether enter the ground station?
- Is the power transmission and the storage of the tether intergrated in one element or are two or more elements used?
- How is the tether distributed on the drum?

4.1 Tether Guidance - Goal Planning, Task Structuring and Goal Analysis

4.1.1 Goal Planning

Current Concept

In the existing ground station, the tether is led over a swivel and a pulley and rolled on the horizontal drum from below (see Figure 4-1). The drum is driven by a spindle motor (not shown in the scheme) with a range of 1 m to distribute the tether on the drum.

The swivel consists of two pulleys with horizontal axes and two side plates. Due to the form of the pulley, the tether should not touch the side plates under normal conditions. The swivel rotates around the vertical axis which allows the tether to run into the swivel with an elevation angle between 0° and 90° and an azimuth angle of 0° to 360° . So the kite can occupy the whole upper-half space. The tether leaves the swivel straight downwards regardless of the position of the kite. A pulley is fixated at the frame of the ground station, leaving it only one rotational freedom, and redirects the tether about 90° towards the drum horizontally on which it is wound from below.

¹Note that the order is changed here, since the results of the *task structuring* affect the requirements.

Figure 4-1.: *Scheme of the tether guidance of the existing ground station*

Tether

The tether and its properties have an important influence on the guidance concept. The tether to be used is made out of UHMWPE by DSM Dyneema[®]. The material is as strong as steel (see Figure A-23 in Appendix A.12), while having a density of only 970 to 980 kg/m³ in comparison to 7,750 to 8,050 kg/m³ for steel. This results in a specific tether weight of one-eighth (1/8) of a steel cable (see Figure A-24 in Appendix A.12).

Another advantage is the high tensile module of 110 GPa of a single yarn [Mar11a, p. 322]. For a tether, it is approximately 80 GPa [Mar11b] due to the woven structure which contracts under load. The friction coefficient of Dyneema to itself (yarn-to-yarn) is 0.07 [DSM08], the coefficient between the Dyneema tether and polished steel is below 0.1 [Mar11b]. The wear of Dyneema due to friction is low - comparable to steel [Mar11b].

Beside these numerous advantages, there are specific properties which must be considered: The tether has two different types of failures: creep and fatigue. The first refers to the break of the tether under static load. If the load is 50% of the breaking load, the tether breaks within 2 to 3 years because of this effect. The latter is caused by dynamic loads due to variations of the tether force, bending and friction. Especially, the bending has to be considered. The bending diameter should be at least 20 times the tether diameter to avoid excessive high stress in the outer fibers [Mar11b] (see Appendix A.13). Additionally, due to the high tensile module, the inner fibers are compressed when the tether is bent.

Which of the aspects affects the wearing of the tether more and the interdependencies between them are still unknown [Mar11b]; but the number of cycles until the tether

breaks is strongly dependent on the maximum load applied (see Figure A-25 and A-26 in Appendix A.12).

These properties of Dyneema influence the decision on the tether guidance as shall be seen later. [Mar11a] and [DSM] provide further information on the material properties.

4.1.2 Task Structuring

Relation Function Model

The tether guidance is described by means of the *relation function model* to determine the requirements of the tether guidance. It consists in essence of four functions (which are displayed in Figure A-20 in Appendix A.7.5 the context):

- guide the tether,
- coil the tether,
- store the tether, and
- uncoil the tether.

To be able to coil the tether, it has to be guided from the kite into the ground station and positioned towards the drum. Additionally, the relative axial movement of the tether towards the drum is necessary to coil it and prevent loops which increase the wear of the tether. Mechanical power has to be provided to enable this axial movement. Before the tether can be uncoiled again, it has to be stored in the ground station.

Due to the guiding and coiling of the tether, slip occurs which increases the wear of the tether. The guiding, coiling, and storing of the tether force the tether to bend which also increases the wear.

Recommended Steps of Action

To generate solution ideas, on the one hand, the method *variation of configuration parameters* (see Appendix A.2.6) is applied, on the other hand, coiling applications in the industry are examined².

The method is applied to the following elements:

- drum,
- fairlead,

²These analogies are not documented in this final thesis.

- pulley, and
- swivel.

The drum fulfills two functions: The conversion of translational into rotational power and vice versa and the storage of the tether. These functions can be integrated into one or more elements. The fairlead - if used - moves the tether axially to the drum and defines its position. The swivel guides the tether into the ground station. Pulleys can be used to redirect the tether within the ground station.

In Table A-7 in Appendix A.14, an overview is provided on the parameters examined. In the following paragraphs, the parameters of the different elements are discussed.

4.1.3 Goal Analysis

As discussed in Section 2.2, a drum and a tether have to be used in the ground station. The diameter of the tether and its length influence the geometry of the elements which stand in contact with it. The drum capacity shall be 1,000 m of 5 mm diameter UHMWPE tether. The nominal breaking force of a tether with 5 mm diameter is 26 kN (see Appendix A.13), so the maximum tether load (11 kN) is 42% of the nominal breaking load.

The wear and tear of the tether determines its lifetime and therefore the reliability of the system. A tether which has to be changed more often increases the downtime, and thus the maintenance costs. This leads to higher energy costs and decreases the system's economic viability. The wear of the tether is caused by three factors besides the load profile: The bending and slipping of the tether and potential loops which stress the tether when the loops are released again. To avoid excessive bending, the minimum bending diameter must not be lower than twenty times the diameter of the tether [Mar11b]. The number of bending cycles of the tether for each kite cycle is dependent on the concept, as will be seen later. The slip of the tether - lengthwise and crosswise - cannot be given quantitatively as there are no reference values. The loops can be measured as numbers per cycle. So far, the number of loops occurring during operation has not been monitored. It is intended to avoid these loops completely. The influences of these three causes for wearing of the tether cannot be compared in their relevance since there is no test data available.

The performance indicators used to evaluate the tether guidance are the same as in the generator concept:

- efficiency,
- costs,
- volume & weight, and
- reliability.

The efficiency includes the power consumption of the axial movement of the drum or the fairlead. The reliability takes the wear of the tether into account.

4.2 Drum

4.2.1 Generation of Solution Ideas

The *generation of solution ideas* comprises three tasks:

- research of applications in the industry,
- the Variation of Configuration Parameters, and
- the composing of solution ideas.

While the results of the first steps are not documented in this thesis, the results of last two steps are given in the following paragraphs.

Variation of Configuration Parameters

Eleven parameters have been evaluated: The shape of the drum and the shape of its surface, the number of drums, the size of the drum, the contact type between the drum and tether, the coupling type, the compactness, the material, the movement type, and the joint freedom.

The *shape of the drum* can be either cylindrical, in the form of a hyperboloid, conic, or double-conic. The *surface of the drum* can either be plain, grooved according to the tether diameter or V-grooved. The drum can be *oriented* horizontally - either along the trailer or across the trailer - or it can be vertically mounted on the trailer. Theoretically, it can also be differently oriented in space, but this has no obvious benefits. The orientation affects the overall assembly of the ground station and the ease of rolling on the tether. The *number of drums* which are used can vary between one and several. Either there is only one drum which transmits the force on the tether and also stores the tether, or a single capstan is used to transmit the power with a second drum to store the tether. Instead of a single capstan, also a double capstan can be used for the force transmission. The *size of the drum(s)* was set at 0.3 m diameter in Section 3.1.2. But it should be kept in mind that this is not necessarily an absolute value but can be changed to a smaller or larger diameter if advantages are expected. Also the length of the drum(s) is changeable. The *contact type* between the tether and the drum(s) is always a surface contact due to the deformation of the tether. Either it has contact with one surface on a plain or concave drum or it has contact with two surfaces if the drum is grooved with a V-shape to increase the friction. The *type of coupling* between the tether and the drum(s) can either be a roll motion or a combined motion of rolling and sliding. This affects the wear

and tear of the tether. The drum can either be made from full material, can be a hollow structure or even an open structure. This *compactness* influences the mass and inertia of the drum and, therefore, the energy needed to change the direction of the rotation. The mass and inertia are also affected by the *material* chosen to build the drum. Steel, alloy, and composites are some possible alternatives. Various *types of movement* can be realized by different *joint freedoms*. The first option is that the drum can only rotate around its axis without any translational movements. The second option is an additional translational movement along the drum axis so the tether can be coiled. The third option provides two rotational freedoms: one around its axis, the other perpendicular. The last option is a combination: two rotational freedoms and one translational freedom. The different options are mainly affected by the decision to use a swivel or not. In Table A-7 in Appendix A.14, the findings are summarized.

From the parameters mentioned above, the alternatives discussed in the following paragraphs focus on the number of drums. The movement type and the location are taken up again in the synthesis of the tether guidance in Section 4.6. These three parameters were considered as the most important ones since they influence other elements of the ground station.

Solution Ideas

Four different drum solutions are derived from the Variation of Configuration Parameters: the simple drum, the spiral drum, the single capstan concept, and the double capstan concept.

The *simple drum* is used in the existing ground station. It consists of one drum which transmits the torque and also stores the tether. The tether is stored in multiple layers on the drum to decrease its size and weight (see Figure 4-2).

Figure 4-2.: *Scheme of the simple drum*

The *spiral drum* is used by Ampyx Power³. It uses one grooved drum with only one layer of tether (see Figure 4-3). Therefore no friction between the coils of the tether can appear.

³Ampyx Power is a Dutch company which pursue a similar airborne wind energy concept as ASSET.

Figure 4-3.: *Scheme of the spiral drum*

The *single capstan* uses two drums: one transmits the torque, the other stores the tether. The tether coming from the kite enters the capstan on one side, coils around it several times and leaves it on the other side to the storage drum (see Figure 4-4).

Figure 4-4.: *Scheme of the single capstan*

The *double capstan* uses three drums: two transmit the torque and one stores the tether. The tethers coils around both drums several times. The two shafts of the capstan are connected via a differential and connected to the electrical machine(s). The tether is bent more often than in other concepts since it has to be bent and straightened twice for every coil at the double capstan (see 4-5).

Figure 4-5.: *Scheme of the double capstan*

4.2.2 Properties Assessment

The proposed drum solutions are compared to each other with respect to the performance indicators defined in the Section 2.3.3: Efficiency, costs, volume & weight, and reliability.

Efficiency

With a *simple drum* or a *spiral drum* it is not necessary to drive an additional shaft. For the *single and double capstan* it is also necessary to drive the storage drum. This increases the power consumption. The storage drum can either be driven by an additional motor or it can be connected to the drive train. Another possibility would be to integrate a spring which is loaded during the reel-out phase and released in the reel-in phase to drive back the drum. The double capstan needs a differential between the two shafts to avoid stress. The bending of the tether dissipates a part of the power; this is especially an issue for the double capstan where the number of bending cycles per kite cycle are the most.

Volume & Weight

The volume of a *simple drum* depends highly on the number of layers possible. If we assume 20 layers of tether and calculate with the average diameter of the drum, a drum with an average diameter of 0.3 m has to be 0.21 m wide (Calculation see Appendix A.13). The *spiral drum* carries only one layer, which means that the required volume increases significantly - compared to the simple drum. If the drum has a diameter of 1 m, the length of the drum has to be 1.25 m to store the entire tether. The *single and double capstan* need more space than the single drum since the capstan(s) have to be integrated. The storage drum on the other hand can carry more layers due to the decreased force of the tether. Therefore more freedom is given for its dimensioning.

For the weight, the comparison is the same as the volume as long as the same materials are used. Possibly, the weight does not increase proportionally with the volume since bigger elements can be built hollow or open.

Costs

The costs of the concepts are mainly dependent on the number and complexity of the elements used. The *simple drum* causes probably the lowest costs since it is only one element which can be either bought off-the-shelf or easily produced. The *spiral drum* is bigger and heavier and needs more material which increases the costs. Additionally, it has also to be grooved to avoid coil contact. This means the production is more complex and therefore more expensive than for the simple drum. The *single capstan* needs a storage drum similar

to the simple drum, and the capstan. The costs will probably be higher than for the simple drum. The *double capstan* needs an additional capstan and a differential - in comparison to the single capstan. This increases the costs significantly.

Reliability

The reliability depends on the number of elements and their possible failures. The more different failures exist and the more often they occur, the lower the reliability is. The wear of the tether is included in this performance indicator.

The *simple drum* and the *spiral drum* have only two kinds of obvious failures: the bearings wear causing increased friction which has a negative effect on the efficiency; and the tether can leave the drum and get clamped between drum and another element, such as the frame. The latter is more probable for the simple drum since the tether is more often at one side of the drum where the chance is higher that it get clamped. In the *single capstan* concept, one more drum is used and its' bearings also wear. Also the tether can slip from the capstan and get caught between the capstan and the frame. The *double capstan* prevents the tether from slipping since it is well defined in the grooves of the capstan drums. The differential on the other side with its gear wheels presents another failure possibility.

The tether wear and tear depends on the number of bendings, the friction, and the load peaks from slack tether⁴. The *single drum* only bends the tether once per cycle, but since the tether is coiled under full load, it abrades on the layers below. Load peaks can appear when the tether leaves its groove (formed by the tether layer underneath). The occurrence of the latter can be reduced with a precise fairlead. The *spiral drum* bends the tether only once per cycle, too. It avoids friction from coil to coil due to its grooves. Instead the tether is only in contact with the drum. The *single capstan* bends the tether three times per cycle (see Figure 4-4). Due to the sliding of the tether from one side of the capstan to the other, some friction is present. Load peaks at the storage drum cannot occur because of the low tether force⁵ there. The *double capstan* bends the tether several times during one cycle, depending on the number of coils around it (see Figure 4-5). The coils do not touch each other therefore the only friction which occur is between the tether and the capstans. Load peaks are not expected for the same reason as for the single capstan.

Property Overview

The properties assessed in the prior paragraphs are compiled and scored in Table 4-1.

⁴There are also load peaks caused by wind gusts, but these are for all concepts equal and therefore not considered here.

⁵The tether force must be high enough to prevent slack tether and is dependent on the speed of the drum because of centrifugal forces.

Drum concept	Efficiency	Costs	Volume & weight	Reliability
Simple drum	2	4	4	2
Spiral drum	2	2	1	4
Single capstan	3	3	3	2
Double capstan	2	2	2	2

Table 4-1.: *Properties of drums*

The simple drum has its' advantages in costs and volume & weight. The spiral drum scores best in reliability and the single capstan promises the best efficiency. The double capstan scores in every category below average.

4.2.3 Decision Making

The properties are weighted to evaluate the different drum concepts. The efficiency is considered as the most important property, the volume & weight is not as important. The costs are assumed to present a rather small share of the total costs of the ground station and have therefore low weight. The reliability is the most uncertain criterion and is therefore given little weight.

Properties	Weighting
Efficiency	9
Costs	1
Volume & weight	3
Reliability	1

Table 4-2.: *Weighting of drum properties*

The matrices of the assessed properties and the weighting are multiplied to obtain the decision matrix.

Drum concept	Eff.	Costs	Vol. & weight	Rel.	Sum	Rank
Simple drum	18	4	12	2	36	2
Spiral drum	18	2	3	4	27	4
Single capstan	27	3	9	2	41	1
Double capstan	18	2	6	2	28	3

Table 4-3.: *Decision matrix for drums*

The decision matrix in Table 4-3 suggests the single capstan as the most suitable concept, followed by the simple drum. But for now, all solutions are kept to configure different tether guidance concepts in the synthesis in Section 4.6.1.

4.3 Fairlead

4.3.1 Generation of Solution Ideas

The *generation of solution ideas* for the fairlead follows the same structure as for the drum: The concepts used in industry applications have been examined but not documented, the *variation of configuration parameters* is carried out and solution ideas are composed.

Variation of Configuration Parameters

The parameters which are evaluated for the fairlead are: shape, location, material, movement type, joint freedom, the negation.

Three different *shapes* of the fairlead are considered: a pulley fairlead with two vertical and two horizontal pulleys leading the tether, a two pulley fairlead with two side plates, or a bell mouth without any moving parts. The conflicting aims are to minimize the moveable parts towards reducing friction. The *location* can be either attached to the drum or it is not directly connected to the drum leaving a larger distance between the elements. While the first location is applicable in a moveable fairlead, the second is more practicable if the fairlead is static (see below). The *material* of the fairlead itself and its interface to the tether can be chosen. Steel, alloy, rubber, and other materials have different friction coefficients and wear differently. This influences the wear of the tether and the fairlead. The *movement types* of the fairlead can either be static (the fairlead does not move) or the fairlead can be moved parallel to the drum axis to coil the tether. Additionally, it can even be moved in radial direction to the drum to adapt to the changing diameter of the drum. A bell mouth can either have no *joint freedom* or can be moved translationally. A pulley fairlead can either have one or two rotational freedoms and optionally a translational movement. The fairlead can also be spared. This means a *negation* of it. In Appendix A.14 the variations are shown in Table A-9.

From the above discussed properties, the material and the joint freedom is not further considered; the movement type and the location are postponed to the synthesis.

Solution Ideas

For the fairlead four solutions are viable: no fairlead, a two pulley fairlead, a four pulley fairlead, and a bell mouth.

It is possible to *omit the fairlead* and not move the drum and still coil the tether neatly if the tether angle at the drum is below 3° . This is known as the 3° -concept⁶ [Pom07]. It is also possible to omit it and allow the tether to coil in disorder. This is probably only a suitable solution if the tether force at the storage drum is low - like in the single and double capstan configuration.

The *two pulley fairlead* uses two pulleys with their axis perpendicular to the axis of the drum to guide the tether and sideplates thus preventing the tether from slipping through the air gap between the pulleys (see Figure 4-6).

Figure 4-6.: *Scheme of the two pulley fairlead*

Instead of the sideplates, the *four pulley fairlead* has two long rolls with their axis parallel to the drum axis (see Figure 4-7).

Figure 4-7.: *Scheme of the four pulley fairlead*

The *bell mouth* has the form of a funnel and does not have any moveable parts. The tether runs through it and glides on the solid metal (see Figure 4-8).

Figure 4-8.: *Scheme of the bell mouth*

⁶This is the value for steel cables, it is assumed that it is also valid for UHMWPE tethers

4.3.2 Properties Assessment

The proposed partial solutions regarding the fairlead are compared with respect to the performance indicators defined in Section 2.3.3: efficiency, costs, volume & weight, and reliability.

Efficiency

The power consumption of the fairlead consists of the power which is needed to move the fairlead - if it is moveable - and the mechanical losses due to contact between the tether and the fairlead.

The *power consumed* for moving the fairlead $P_{FL,move}$ is dependent of the tether speed v_T , the tether force F_T and the tether angle γ . This part of the power consumption is independent of the type of fairlead that is used.

The *mechanical losses* due to contact between the tether and the fairlead $P_{FL,contact}$ can be separated into friction losses between them and mechanical losses in the bearings of the pulleys and rolls.

It is assumed that the *friction losses* between tether and fairlead $P_{FL,sliding}$ are proportional to the relative speed $v_{rel,T,P}$ and the normal force $F_{n,T,P}$ ⁷.

The *losses of the bearing* $P_{FL,bearing}$ are assumed to be proportional to the rotation speed of the pulley n_P and the normal force $F_{n,T,P}$.

For both *pulley fairleads*, the power consumption should be almost the same, since in both cases the tether is guided by the pulleys. The rolls and side plates are barely in contact with the tether.

The *bell mouth* omits the bearings, therefore the losses only consist of friction losses between the tether and the bell mouth. These are significantly increased compared to the losses of the pulleys due to the increased relative speed.

Costs

The investment costs of the two pulley fairlead are probably slightly lower than the four pulley fairlead. The bell mouth is less expensive than the pulley fairleads since it only consists of one part.

Volume & Weight

While the pulley fairleads are almost equal in size and mass, the bell mouth is smaller and lighter.

⁷It is assumed that the friction coefficient is the same for all configurations.

Reliability

The bell mouth does not have any rotating parts and is therefore less exposed to failures than the pulley fairleads. But the wear of the bell mouth is much higher because of the increased friction to the tether.

Property Overview

In Table 4-4, the assessed properties are given. If no fairlead is used, the efficiency is the highest and costs, and volume & weight are the lowest, but the reliability is worse.

Concept	Efficiency	Costs	Volume & weight	Reliability
No fairlead	4	4	4	1
Two pulley fairlead	3	3	2	3
Four pulley fairlead	3	3	2	4
Bell mouth	2	3	4	2

Table 4-4.: *Properties of fairleads*

4.3.3 Decision Making

The weighting of the properties in Table 4-5 enables a decision to be made on which concept is viable for the redesign of the ground station. The efficiency is very important since it directly influences the total efficiency of the ground station. The reliability is given a medium importance. The costs and volume & weight are given a low importance since the costs present only a small share of the total costs and the dimensions and weight of the fairlead are negligible in comparison to the dimensions of other elements, as for instance the drum.

Properties	Weighting
Efficiency	9
Costs	1
Volume & weight	1
Reliability	3

Table 4-5.: *Weighting of fairlead properties*

The decision matrix in Table 4-6 shows the results of the combination of the assessed properties and their weighting.

The omittance of the fairlead seems to be the most favorable solution, but it has to kept in mind that either the whole drum has to be moved if the tether is to be coiled neatly

Fairlead concept	Eff.	Costs	Vol. & weight	Rel.	Sum	Rank
No fairlead	36	4	4	3	47	1
Two pulley fairlead	27	3	2	9	41	3
Four pulley fairlead	27	3	2	12	44	2
Bell mouth	18	3	4	6	31	4

Table 4-6.: *Decision matrix for fairleads*

or the tether will be coiled in disorder. The four pulley fairlead is chosen as the preferred fairlead concept if the drum is static.

4.4 Swivel

4.4.1 Generation of Solution Ideas

The swivel is in fact a first fairlead which guides the tether into the ground station. Specific requirements are the changing position of the kite which causes the swivel to turn around the vertical axis for the azimuth angle and changes the angle of tether contact to the pulley. Therefore, the swivel must be beared with a rotational freedom and the pulley must be designed to stand the changing forces. Since the fairlead has already been discussed, only the location of the swivel is discussed here explicitly, the other parameters can be taken from above⁸.

The location of the swivel can either be at the top of the ground station or at the side. If it is mounted on top of the ground station, it is understood that the kite can be located in the entire upper half-space with the ground station being static. If the swivel is located on a side, the transmission of the tether force is lower, which reduces the moment on the ground station, but it restricts the zone where the kite can fly to an azimuth angle of about 180° or it prerequisites a ground station which turns on its vertical axis. The placement on the side is therefore eliminated.

For the swivel, two solutions are possible: the four pulley swivel and the two pulley swivel⁹.

The swivel can be positioned at the top (center, long edge, short edge, corner) of the ground station or at the side. This depends on the chosen tether guidance concept and is therefore discussed in the synthesis.

⁸In Appendix A.14 in Table A-10 the swivel variations are displayed.

⁹The negation of the swivel is not an option since the tether must enter the ground station in a defined way. The bell mouth is not viable due to the high forces which occur at the swivel

4.4.2 Properties Assessment and Decision Making

The proposed partial solutions regarding the fairlead are compared with respect to the efficiency. Costs, volume & weight, and reliability have already been covered in the discussion about the fairlead.

The power losses of the swivel P_{SW} depend on the tether speed, the tether force, the angle of contact, and the friction coefficient between tether and pulleys and inside the bearing of the pulleys¹⁰. In Appendix A.13, the calculation is carried out.

The four pulley swivel is the preferred choice since the same advantage as in the examination of the fairlead is present: the reliability is slightly higher than in the two pulley swivel.

4.5 Pulley

4.5.1 Generation of Solution Ideas

The pulley has been mentioned already as part of the fairlead and swivel but it is also an independent element used to redirect the tether. The variation parameters considered are: shape, location, number of pulleys used, size, contact type, coupling type, material, joint freedom, and negation.

The *shape* of the pulley can be - as the drum - either cylindrical, hyperboloid, conic, or double conic. The shape's main purpose is to prevent the tether from slipping of the pulley. The *location* of the pulley is categorized according to the tether angle it produces. Obvious possibilities are a 90° or a 180° angle but also other angles are possible. The *number of pulleys* used can be varied. It is possible to use one, two, or even more pulleys to redirect the tether. The number of pulleys impacts the mechanical losses on the one side, but can improve the reliability of the tether guidance on the other. The *size* of the pulley(s) has to be defined taking into account the tether bending, mass and inertia of the pulley, and the arrangement of the pulley in the ground station. The *contact type* is a result of the chosen shape: While the tether is convex, the cylindrical and conic pulleys are planar; in contrast, the hyperboloid and double-conic pulleys are concave. A concave form drives the tether back into the middle when deviated to the sides but causes a slightly higher friction. The *coupling type* of the tether on the pulley can be described as a combination of gliding and rolling; whereas a pure rolling is practically not possible and a pure gliding would mean a not turning pulley. The *material* used for the pulley affects the above mentioned coupling due to the different friction coefficients. The choice between steel, alloy, and others, also has influence on the mass and inertia of the pulleys. The pulley(s) can be bedded stiff leaving only one rotational joint freedom. In contrast, they can be *jointed* with either two or three rotational degrees of freedoms. A

¹⁰The losses due to the rotation of the swivel around its vertical axis are neglected.

negation of the pulley is also possible; not using a pulley would decrease the mechanical losses but lower the accuracy guiding the tether. The pulley variations are shown in Appendix A.14.

The only properties which are further considered are the negation and the number of pulleys. The optimal solution is to omit the pulley, if possible, thus no additional losses are caused. The arrangement of the elements can make it necessary to redirect the tether inside the ground station. Then one pulley may be needed. An obvious advantage for the use of more than one pulley has not been found.

4.5.2 Properties Assessment and Decision Making

The mechanical losses if a pulley is used, depend on the tether force, the contact angle, and the tether speed. If a pulley is used, it causes costs, adds weight, and increases the volume. The reliability is decreased since every additional element presents another source of failure¹¹.

If a single or double capstan is used, there is no reason to include an additional pulley since the redirection of the tether to the storage drum can be done by the capstan. If the simple drum or spiral drum is used and moveable, the tether does not have to be redirected since it can also be led vertically on the drum. If the simple or spiral drum is static, a pulley will probably be necessary to increase the free tether length in front of the drum to reduce the force if a fairlead is used. If no fairlead is used, the free tether length must even be longer to maintain a tether angle of 3° on the drum.

4.6 Tether Guidance - Generation of Solution Ideas, Properties Assessment and Decision Making

4.6.1 Generation of Solution Ideas

The partial solutions for the drum, fairlead, swivel, and pulley can be combined to generate solutions for the tether guidance. In Table 4-7 the partial solutions are compiled¹².

The partial solutions are examined in regard to their compatibility to each other. Some of the partial solutions are dependent on each other:

- A static drum without a fairlead must use a pulley if the tether is to be coiled neatly.

¹¹Above it was mentioned that the pulley increases the reliability of the tether guidance. Nevertheless if the tether guidance allows its elimination due to the arrangement of elements in the ground station, the reliability is higher.

¹²Partial solutions which have been discarded are not listed.

Partial concepts		Partial solutions			
Drum concept	Simple drum	Spiral drum	Single capstan	Double capstan	
Drum movement	Static	Translational along axis			
Fairlead concept	No fairlead	Four pulley			
Fairlead movement	Static	Translational			
Swivel concept	Four pulley				
Swivel position	Top center	Top long edge	Top short edge	Top corner	Side
Pulley	No pulley	One pulley			

Table 4-7.: Morphologic box for tether guidance concepts

- If a fairlead is used together with a static drum, it can be either static or be moved translationally parallel to the drum axis. A pulley can be used to increase the distance between the fairlead and the drum in the case of a static fairlead¹³. If the fairlead is moved, the free tether length also should be increased to decrease the force necessary to move it¹⁴.
- A moveable drum can use a static fairlead or can omit it, an obvious reason why both, the drum and the fairlead, should be moveable is not known. A pulley is optional.

A total of 9 out of 12 theoretical solutions remain not taking into account the various drum concepts and the position of the swivel. After all drum concepts are all considered, the position of the swivel is chosen. Four different swivel positions on top of the ground station are possible: center, long edge, short edge, and corner. In the *center* of the ground station, the moment acting on the ground station is independent of the kite position, but the space for the fairleads and drum(s) cannot be optimally utilized since only half of the volume of the ground station can be effectively used. The *long edge* of the ground station provides the most space for a moveable drum. The swivel on the *short edge* offers the longest free tether length favoring an efficient fairlead movement or even the omittance of an axial movement (3°-concept). Placing the swivel in the *corner* uses the least space but a second pulley cannot be omitted if the drum shall be horizontal and is therefore no longer considered.

In addition to the compositions of the partial solutions, the arrangement of these elements could be varied¹⁵.

Four concepts, with well-suited partial solutions, are chosen to be compared to each other:

- single capstan concept with static drum and moving fairlead, the swivel at the short edge, without pulley,

¹³This is the implementation of the 3°-concept

¹⁴It must be kept in mind that the decreased losses of the fairlead movement have to compensate the losses of the additional pulley.

¹⁵This is beyond the focus of this thesis.

- double capstan concept with static drum and static fairlead, the swivel at the short edge, without additional pulley,
- simple drum concept with a moveable drum, the swivel at the center, without fairlead and pulley, and
- spiral drum concept with moveable drum and pulley, the swivel at the long edge, without fairlead.

The properties of these configurations are examined in the following section. In Figures A-33 to A-36 in Appendix A.17.2 the tether guidance schemes can be found.

4.6.2 Properties Assessment

Weighting of Element Properties

The properties of the partial solutions have already been estimated. To compare the different proposed concepts, it is necessary to weight the elements in regard to their properties¹⁶.

The *efficiency* for all properties is weighted equally high¹⁷.

The *costs* for the drum are substantially higher than for the fairlead and the swivel, therefore the effect of changes in drum costs is higher than for other elements. The fairlead consists of two pulleys in addition to other parts, thus the pulley is less expensive and affects the total costs of the tether guidance C_{TG} to a lesser degree.

The *volume & weight* of the drum is much higher in comparison to the fairlead, the swivel, and the pulley. The fairlead affects the needed space more than the swivel because it is built inside of the ground station where other elements also have to be positioned. The swivel, in contrast, is on top of the ground station where no other elements have to be placed. Little space is needed to integrate the pulley.

Also in regard to the *reliability* the drum(s) are weighted the most: in contrast to the other elements the tether is either bent several times (in the double capstan) or coils abrading on each other (in the single capstan and in the simple drum). For the fairlead and the pulley the position is well defined, thus the differences in the reliability are smaller. The swivel has to cope with changing tether angles, so its reliability is weighted higher than that of the fairlead and pulley.

The weighting of the properties are summarized in Table 4-8.

¹⁶For instance the volume of the drum is significantly larger than that of the pulley. Therefore it must be higher weighted when the different concepts are compared.

¹⁷The efficiency of the tether guidance η_{TG} is the product of all partial efficiencies.

Properties	Drum	Fairlead	Swivel	Pulley
Efficiency	9	9	9	9
Costs	9	3	3	1
Volume & weight	9	3	1	1
Reliability	9	1	3	1

Table 4-8.: *Weighting of properties of tether guidance elements*

In the following paragraphs each performance indicator is examined. The properties of the four elements for each concept are weighted, and the sum and the rank calculated.

Efficiency

The weighted efficiency rating of the different concepts is shown in Table 4-9¹⁸.

Concept	Drum	Fairlead	Swivel	Pulley	Sum	Rank
Single capstan	27	27	27	36	117	1
Double capstan	18	27	27	36	108	3
Simple drum	18	36	27	36	117	1
Spiral drum	18	36	27	18	99	4

Table 4-9.: *Efficiencies of the tether guidance concepts (weighted)*

The single capstan concept and the simple drum have the highest efficiencies. The spiral drum concept uses a pulley to redirect the tether thus lowering the efficiency.

Costs

The costs of the different concepts are compared in Table 4-10.

Concept	Drum	Fairlead	Swivel	Pulley	Sum	Rank
Single capstan	27	9	9	4	49	2
Double capstan	18	9	9	4	40	4
Simple drum	36	12	9	4	61	1
Spiral drum	18	12	9	3	42	3

Table 4-10.: *Costs of the tether guidance concepts (weighted)*

The costs of the simple drum are the lowest due to the least expensive drum.

¹⁸The values are calculated by multiplication of the weight and the score of the partial concepts.

Volume & Weight

The volume & weight of the tether guidance concepts are comparatively summarized in Table 4-11.

Concept	Drum	Fairlead	Swivel	Pulley	Sum	Rank
Single capstan	27	6	2	4	39	2
Double capstan	18	6	2	3	29	3
Simple drum	36	12	2	4	54	1
Spiral drum	9	6	2	4	21	4

Table 4-11.: *Volume & weight of the tether guidance concepts (weighted)*

Also in this category, the simple drum ranks first and the single capstan second. The spiral drum due to its large size which needs the most space and is the heaviest.

Reliability

The reliability of the concepts is compared in Table 4-12.

Concept	Drum	Fairlead	Swivel	Pulley	Sum	Rank
Single capstan	18	4	9	4	35	2
Double capstan	18	1	9	3	31	4
Simple drum	18	1	9	4	32	3
Spiral drum	36	1	9	3	49	1

Table 4-12.: *Reliability of the tether guidance concepts (weighted)*

In this category, the spiral drum concept ranks higher than the others due to lack of contact between tether coils next to each other on the drum. In the single capstan, the tether is guided by a fairlead thus improving the quality of the winding on the drum significantly¹⁹.

Property Overview

In Table 4-13, the results of the Tables 4-9 to 4-12 are summarized.

¹⁹The decreased tether force of the coiled tether in the single and double capstan concepts in comparison to the simple and spiral drum concepts is not represented in this evaluation.

Concept	Efficiency	Costs	Volume & weight	Reliability
Single capstan	57	49	39	35
Double capstan	42	39	29	34
Simple drum	51	61	54	32
Spiral drum	48	40	21	53

Table 4-13.: *Properties of tether guidance concepts*

4.6.3 Decision Making

In the last step, the properties of the four proposed concepts have been evaluated. In this step, the properties are weighted and the concepts compared.

In Table 4-14, the properties of the tether guidance are weighted.

Efficiency and costs are given high importance, volume & weight and reliability are weighted medium. This reflect the focus of the design process (compare to Section 2.2).

Properties	Weight
Efficiency	9
Costs	9
Volume & weight	3
Reliability	3

Table 4-14.: *Weighting of tether guidance concept properties*

The results are shown in Table 4-15²⁰. The simple drum reaches the highest overall score, leading in the categories efficiency, costs, and volume & weight. Only the reliability is lower than in other concepts. The single capstan places second beating the simple drum only in the category reliability and tying for efficiency while it places second in costs and volume & weight. The double capstan places last in costs and third (ahead of the spiral drum) in efficiency and volume & weight. The reliability is as high as for the single capstan concept. The spiral drum has the highest reliability but is also the largest and heaviest concept with the lowest efficiency. The costs are valued higher than the two leading concepts and slightly lower than those of the double capstan concept.

Concept	Eff.	Costs	Vol. & weight	Rel.	Sum	Rank
Single capstan	1053	441	117	105	1716	2
Double capstan	972	360	90	105	1527	3
Simple drum	1053	549	162	96	1860	1
Spiral drum	891	378	78	147	1494	4

Table 4-15.: *Decision matrix for tether guidance concepts*

²⁰The evaluations of the performance indicators are multiplied with their weightings to calculate the decision matrix.

This chapter have described the solution space of the tether guidance and restricted it to suitable solutions. The properties have been assessed and decisions (on a early knowledge basis) have been made.

The evaluation of the concepts are based on discussions with experts in different fields and on rough estimations of the properties. The results are highly sensitive on the weighting which is subjective. Therefore these results should be treated with great care. It is recommended that tests be carried out and models developed to support the design process (see Chapter 7).

Chapter 5 Ground Station - Ensuring Goal Achievement

5.1 Interdependencies between Concepts

The generator concept and the tether guidance have been discussed in this theses; so far they have been treated independently of each other.

Therefore, potential interdependencies of the two concepts are addressed here - without going into detail.

The *diameter of the torque drum* presents an interface between the two concepts. The variation of the drum diameter influences the required gearbox ratio and/or the chosen electrical machine in the generator concept on the one hand, and, on the other hand, the wear of the tether.

The *drum concept affects the drive train*. If the single or double capstan concept is used, the storage drum has to be driven in addition to the capstan(s). This could be done by gear wheels, belts, chains, or other power transmitting elements.

Other interdependencies are not known.

5.2 Ground Station Concepts

The proposed generator concepts from Chapter 3 are:

- one rigidly connected, directly-driven squirrel cage induction machine and
- two direct-driven clutch coupled permanent magnet synchronous machine.

The tether guidance concepts discussed in Chapter 4 which seem the most suitable are:

- the simple drum concept with a moveable drum and
- the single capstan concept with a static drum and a moving fairlead

Since no adverse interdependencies are known so far, these concepts can be combined with each other to define the ground station concept.

Here it does not make any sense to suggest one final solution, since all four combinations seem to be viable and only further investigation can identify which generator concept is the most favorable.

5.3 Possible Goal Deviations

The purpose of the ground station is to prove the technical and economic feasibility of a pumping cycle with kites as the chosen airborne wind energy concept (see Section 2.2). Here the requirements of the transportability and efficiency are focused¹.

The *transportability* is primarily dependent on the weight of the ground station which must not exceed 2,800 kg. With regard to the estimations made in Chapters 3 and 4, it is highly probable that this weight restriction can be upheld with the suitable electrical machine concept. The spiral drum concept is rather difficult to fit on a trailer, the other tether guidance concepts should be feasible.

An increase in the total *efficiency* of the ground station is probable, although specific values require further investigation and testing.

To estimate the *costs of energy* for the kite power system the efficiency and costs are required. Therefore simulations have to be run and prices inquired to get viable predictions.

¹The costs cannot be deviated as long as no financial framework is known. The reliability is a minor issue in this development phase, since the operation time is far away from the life time of elements used.

Chapter 6 Reflection on Methodology

The application of the *munich procedure model* as methodology used in this thesis is reflected in this chapter. The practical experience of combining the *munich procedure model* with the *systems engineering* approach is evaluated, the role of the guiding questions of the seven steps of the *munich procedure model* is described and the application of the methodology in the context of a thesis is discussed.

6.1 Combination of the Munich Procedure Model with Systems Engineering

In the Technicial University of Delft, *systems engineering* is the standard process taught for the development of products. Therefore it was suggested to use *systems engineering* as a guideline for the design of the ground station. *Systems engineering* can be classified as a philosophy¹ and the *munich procedure model* as a methodology (see Figure 6-1) which uses methods and tools. Thus, theoretically it should be possible to combine SE and *munich procedure model*.

Figure 6-1.: *The classification of systems engineering and the munich procedure model derived from [Rei04, p. 100 ff.]*

In the application during the design process, however, the distinct definition of project phases made it necessary to limit the *systems engineering* on the terminology of the elements and the derivation of requirements.

It seems that a combination of both approaches is not possible making communication between project partners using the two distinct approaches a potential source of misunderstanding.

¹[Rei04] does differentiate between philosophy and methodology. *Systems engineering* is not mentioned explicitly, but a comparison to other described philosophies suggest to classify also *systems engineering* as one of them.

6.2 The Application of the Munich Procedure Model on the Design of the Ground Station

The *munich procedure model* has been adapted to the specific task of designing a ground station for a kite power system. In the following sections the experience gained in these steps is summarized. In Appendix A.1 the guiding questions for each step are listed.

6.2.1 Goal Planning

The design of the ground station has been based on an operational level. The definition of the design task, an overview of the kite power system and a review of the existing ground station have given a systematic description of the product. The results have been able to be structured with ease. The anticipation of results and the development of future and result models have been seen as an issue which is more suitable to a strategic level.

6.2.2 Goal Analysis

The ground station requirements have been derived from evaluating their purpose and constraints as proposed by *systems engineering* [vT06]. The early phase of the product development process and the missing integration of other stakeholders have not allowed a quantitative specification of the requirements. Potential foreseeable conflicts of requirements have been documented. Nevertheless, it is essential for the success of the product to consider other stakeholders in the future phases of the design process. The documentation of the requirements in a list has been waived, and instead a text description has been compiled.

6.2.3 Task Structuring

The abstract system description has been carried out in the form of the *relation function model*. The flow oriented function model has been developed independently but has not added any value to the *relation function model*. The links from goals to solution attributes have not been traced, since without customer needs the linking is not reasonable. The identification of strengths and weaknesses would have required a comparable product. Since there has been no access to competitors' products, this step has been omitted. The degrees of freedom have been defined as elements which are active and influence other elements of the ground station. The recommendation of steps of action have included (beside the degrees of freedom), the most important adverse functions and the purpose of the kite power system.

6.2.4 Generation of Solution Ideas

This step has been carried out several times. In the design process, first available solutions have been searched and then new solutions have been generated by the *variation of configuration parameters*. However, in the documentation the existing industry applications have been used as examples in the theoretical frame of the assessed configurations of the variation of parameters, thus providing a more coherent structure. The combination of solution ideas has been carried out as a separate step in the Chapters 3 and 4, after the subconcepts have been discussed, to enable a distinct comparison of these syntheses.

6.2.5 Properties Assessment

The properties used to compare the possible solutions are defined in *task structuring* to ensure that properties of different subconcepts (e. g. drum and pulley) can be combined to evaluate the superior level (e. g. tether guidance). The early phase of the design process presupposes simple properties which have been established by estimates and some basic calculations instead of a model. The results have been evaluated in the subsequent step, *decision making*.

6.2.6 Decision Making

The solutions gathered have been compared to each other with respect to their properties and weighting. It has not been possible to suggest a single solution but rather to propose several concepts which have to be further evaluated by means of tests or models. The results have been interpreted carefully, since they are mainly based on assumptions. The thesis itself represents the documentation of the results of the decision process.

6.2.7 Ensuring Goal Achievement

Interdependancies of the generator concept and tether guidance have been listed and the combination of concepts has been addressed in this last step. A risk analysis has to be carried out later in the design process.

6.3 The Application of the Munich Procedure Model in the Context of a Thesis

The recursive application of the *munich procedure model* (see Introduction) has been helpful in the design process itself, but has presented a challenge to the document structure. The hierarchical structure of a document with its chapters and sections cannot be satisfied easily by the iterative application of the *munich procedure model*. The various levels of detail each step would result in unequal chapter lengths and many heading levels. For instance, the tether guidance is subordinately assigned to *generation of solution ideas* for the ground station design but takes a substantially larger part in the thesis as in comparison to the *goal analysis*. Therefore some adaption in the document structure has been required. The interdependencies of the steps required several iterations when new partial solutions reveal new properties. These properties have then been assessed for the existing solutions. Such small iterations do not seem to favor a coherent thesis structure and are therefore not documented explicitly.

The *properties assessment* and the *decision making* have been regarded as a challenge to carry out since little information about the properties assessed has been available. This has to be taken into consideration in the future design process.

Chapter 7 Conclusion and Recommendations

In this thesis, several design proposals for a new ground station for the kite power system at ASSET have been developed on the basis of the *munich procedure model*.

The elements of the kite power system at the Technical University of Delft have been identified and brought into relationship to each other. Special focus has been put on the existing ground station, which has been examined and systematically described for the first time. The requirements of a new ground station have been derived from its purpose and constraints. The generator concept and the tether guidance have been identified as the most important elements of the ground station. To evaluate these two elements, four performance indicators: efficiency, costs, volume & weight, and reliability, have been introduced.

The generator concept has been divided into the three subconcepts: drive train, gearbox, and type of the electrical machine. For these subconcepts, several sound solution alternatives have been found. These alternatives of subconcepts have been combined in a morphologic box to obtain four alternative configurations for the generator concept:

- rigidly connected, directly-driven squirrel cage induction machine,
- clutch coupled direct-driven concept with two permanent magnet synchronous machines,
- clutch coupled direct-driven concept with two squirrel cage induction machines, and
- clutch coupled, mechanically geared concept with two squirrel cage induction machines.

The solutions for the tether guidance have been derived from applying the *variation of configuration parameters* on the four subordinated elements: drum, fairlead, swivel, and pulley. By combining the partial solutions found, four different concepts have been evaluated:

- single capstan concept with a static drum and a moving fairlead,
- double capstan concept with a static drum and static fairlead,
- simple drum which is moveable, without fairlead, and
- the moveable spiral drum, with a pulley but without fairlead.

The interface between the generator concept and the tether guidance has been discussed briefly in Chapter 5 to point out critical issues for the subsequent phases of the ground station design.

Even if the early stage of the design process has not allowed a detailed comparison of all elements, the solution space of ground station concepts, which has first been created and then afterwards reduced to alternative solutions, is documented in this thesis for the first time.

This thesis represents the first step to a new ground station. New questions emerge from the discussed aspects in this thesis which point out the need for research in different fields:

- different types of electrical machines need to be modeled to enable a sound choice and integration,
- tether guidance concepts need to be tested to determine their properties,
- the lowest achievable energy costs of a kite power system have to be determined to focus development on the corresponding market segments, and
- an intensive risk analysis should be carried out to determine possible causes for failures and how to avoid or minimize them.

The market potential of wind energy will be expanded by using tethered flying devices at high altitudes where conventional wind turbines cannot be operated. The design of a ground station is one of the critical issues to be solved in order to place a kite power system on the market. In this thesis, two critical elements of the ground station have been illuminated: the generator concept and the tether guidance. Further success will depend on the lowest costs of energy that are achievable. Ultimately, the costs will determine if the winds in high altitudes can be used as a new alternative energy source to conventional wind turbines.

Glossary

active tether length

Defined as the difference of the tether length between beginn and end of the reel-out phase. It is determined by the flight height of the kite (own definition).

assembly

An integrated set of components that comprises a defined part of the subsystem [vT06, p. 1-6].

bell mouth

A funnel through which the tether is guided (own definition).

clarification of requirements

Is a checklist to avoid overlooking important aspects during the goal analysis [dev05].

component

Comprised of multiple parts; a cleanly identified item [vT06, p. 1-6].

converter

A machine that converts electric current from one kind to another [Far11].

cycle

Defines the time in between two consecutive reel-out phases of the kite. At the beginning of each cycle the kite is approximately at the same position (own definition).

decision making

Is the sixth step of the munich procedure model in which the solution ideas are evaluated and decisions made. [Lin09, p. 49].

doubly-fed wound rotor induction machine

An induction machine that has windings on both stationary and rotating parts, where both windings transfer significant power between shaft and electrical system. Doubly-fed induction machines are useful in applications that require varying speed of the machine's shaft for a fixed power system frequency [Far11].

drive train

Defined as the mechanical element which delivers the power from the drum to the electrical machine or vice versa (Own definition).

drum

There are two distinct types of drums: The torque drum which converts the translational into rotational power and vice versa and the storage drum which keep the tether stored in coils. One drum can also fulfill both functions (own definition).

electrical excited synchronous machine

A synchronous machine which in the magnetic field of the rotor is caused by external excitation (own definition).

electrical machine

An electrical machine is a device that converts mechanical energy to electrical energy or vice versa [Far11].

element

Umbrella term for system, subsystem, assembly, component, and part (own definition).

ensuring goal achievement

Is the seventh and last step of the munich procedure model in which risks are recognized, evaluated, and reduced [Lin09, p. 49].

fairlead

Guides the tether and either moves or guide the tether on a moving drum (own definition).

free tether length

Defined as the distance between the last contact of the tether to another element to the contact of the tether to the drum. The longer this distance is, the lower the force to move the tether axially with a fairlead (own definition).

full load hours

Defined as the annual energy yield fed into the grid by a system, divided by the nominal power of this system. It is used for conventional wind turbines to express their utilization and depends on the wind turbines itself and the site. In the case of wind turbines, the nominal power is the peak power of the turbine at nominal wind speed. For the kite power system, it is used as the ratio of annual energy yield and electrical net power at nominal wind speed (own definition).

gearbox

Provides speed and torque conversions from a rotating power source to another device using gear ratios [Far11].

generation of solution ideas

Is the fourth step of the munich procedure model in which solutions are generated, structured and combined [Lin09, p. 49].

generator concept

Describes the integration of electrical machines in the ground station. It comprises the choice of the drive train concept, the gearbox, and the type of the electrical machines (own definition).

goal analysis

Is the second step of the munich procedure model in which the final condition is described by the definition of requirements [Lin09, p. 48].

goal planning

Is the first step of the munich procedure model in which the actual situation is analyzed [Lin09, p. 48].

ground station

Is a subsystem of the kite power system and comprises the elements: Electrical machine, power infrastructure, trailer, tether guidance, sled, IT infrastructure, energy storage, drive train, and body work (own definition).

induction machine

An asynchronous alternating current machine, in which the windings of two electric circuits rotate with respect to each other and power is transferred from one circuit to the other by electromagnetic induction [Far11].

kite control unit

Is the flying device which steers the kite. It is connected to the ground station by the tether (own definition).

kite power system

Harvests wind energy from high altitudes by means of a kite and converts the power of the wind into electrical power. It comprises the elements: Kite control unit, communication module, tether, wind sensor, kite, control stand, and ground station (own definition).

load profile

A graph of the variation of the rotation speed, torque, and power versus time (own definition on the basis of [Wik11]).

method

Is an exact instruction to achieve a given aim systematically [Rei04].

methodology

Is a functional linked collection of methods and tools to support the product development [Rei04].

morphologic box

A method to structure partial solutions. It is used when a complex problem definition and many solutions were generated [Lin09, p. 281].

motor controller

Varies the speed of the electrical machine by generating its supply frequency. It can have additional functions like overcurrent protection or speed control [PNP04, p. 15].

munich procedure model

Was developed at the TUM and combines the advantages of several known procedure models used in product development.

pairwise comparison

A method to evaluate solutions. It is used when properties are rather quantitatively than qualitatively assessable [Lin09, p. 289].

part

The lowest level of separately identifiable items [vT06, p. 1-6].

permanent magnet synchronous machine

A synchronous machine which in the magnetic field of the rotor is caused by permanent magnets (own definition).

philosophy

Is the guiding principle of the product development [Rei04].

product development process

Comprises the life cycle phases: product planning, product development and design, and production process preparation [Lin09, p. 330].

properties assessment

Is the fifth step of the munich procedure model in which the specifications of relevant solution properties are determined [Lin09, p. 49].

pulley

Redirects the tether without extracting any power beside the mechanical losses due to friction (own definition).

reel-in

Describes the phase when the kite is reeled-in and energy has to be invested into the system (own definition).

reel-out

Describes the phase when the kite is reeled-out and energy is delivered by the system; (own definition).

relation function model

A method to describe an element and in a complex problem definition by relating the functions of the element to each other [Lin09, p. 301].

squirrel cage induction machine

An induction machine with a rotor with a cylindrical winding having copper bars around the periphery parallel to the axis [Far11].

subsystem

An integrated set of assemblies which performs a cleanly and clearly separated function; involving similar technical skills, or possibly a separate supplier [vT06, p. 1-6].

swivel

Leads the tether from outside the ground station into it (own definition).

synchronous machine

An induction machine, whose rotating speed is proportional to the frequency of the alternating current supply and independent of the load [Far11].

system

An integrated set of subsystems and assemblies to accomplish a defined objective [vT06, p. 1-6].

systems engineering

An interdisciplinary approach and means to enable the realization of successful systems [vT06, p. 1-5].

task structuring

Is the third step of the munich procedure model in which the problem is described on an abstract level and the design process is defined [Lin09, p. 48].

tether guidance

Mechanism which leads the tether from outside of the ground station to the storage drum.

tool

Materials and information which support the application of methods [Rei04].

type

Is the general character or structure held in common by a number of electrical machine considered as a group or class [Far11].

ultra-high-molecular-weight polyethylene

A polyethylene with long chains [Mar11a, p. 1].

variation of configuration parameters

Is a method to expand the solution space and optimize existing solution ideas [Lin09, p. 311].

wound rotor induction machine

An singly-fed induction machine with one winding set actively participating in the energy conversion process [Far11].

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A Appendix

A.1 Munich Procedure Model - Guiding Questions

The steps of the *munich procedure model* provide guiding questions to support the developer in the design process [Lin10]. These questions are listed here.

Goal Planning:

- How can situations be analyzed?
- How can analysis results be structured and interdependencies be presented?
- How can changes in attributes be estimated and how can results be anticipated?
- How can alternative future and result models be developed?
- How can specific steps of action and measures be deduced?

Goal Analysis:

- How can requirements be defined?
- How can requirements conflict be discovered?
- How can requirements be structured and weighted?
- How can requirements be documented?

Task Structuring:

- How can systems be described on an abstract level?
- How can goals be linked to solution attributes?
- How can strengths and weaknesses be identified?
- How can degrees of freedom for the development be identified?
- How can recommended actions be deduced for the development?

Generation of Solution Ideas:

- How can available solutions be found?
- How can new solutions be generated?
- How can discrepancies be resolved?
- How can available solution ideas be structured and the scope of concepts be increased?

- How can solution ideas of various subproblems be combined into an overall idea concept?

Properties Assessment:

- How can assessable properties be identified?
- How can a property analysis be prepared?
- How can a property analysis be conducted?
- How can analysis results be evaluated?

Decision Making:

- How can appropriate solution ideas be selected?
- How can an evaluation be prepared?
- How can alternatives be evaluated?
- How can the results of evaluation be interpreted?
- How can decision processes be documented?

Ensuring Goal Achievement:

- How can goal deviations and their causes be identified?
- How can errors, causes and effects be linked?
- How can risk be evaluated?
- How can risk be reduced?

A.2 Methods Used

A.2.1 Checklist of Requirements

The *clarification of requirements* supports the definition of the requirements well. It is especially suitable when concrete requirements for components or parts are determined. In this thesis, the lack of stakeholders involved in the design process has only allowed to define general requirements which have not been able to quantify.

A.2.2 Relation Function Model

The *relation function model* has been used to develop an abstract model of the ground station and its elements. It has been experienced that avoiding ambiguity is a challenge. The functions can be segmented into subfunctions which provokes inconsistency and redundancy if not handled with great care. The function “increase rotation speed” could not be formulated before the restrictions of electrical machines have been examined.

A.2.3 Pairwise Comparison

The *pairwise comparison* has been used for the assessment of properties for the electrical machine concepts. It is more convenient to use than a direct score evaluation when properties are unknown before the *properties assessment* and solution ideas are diverse.

A.2.4 Decision Making Matrix

The *decision making matrix* (weighted rating) has been used in all concepts and subconcepts. While presenting an elegant method to picture the differences of compared solutions it implicates a non-existing accuracy which leads easily to premature decisions. Depending on which person evaluates the properties, the results vary significantly. Therefore it has been used with great care and other solution alternatives has not been excluded unless significant disadvantages have been detected.

A.2.5 Morphologic Box

The *morphologic box* has been used to synthesize the generator concept and the tether guidance from the according subconcepts. Instead of the regular use with “partial problems” [Lin09], “partial concepts” have been used.

A.2.6 Variation of Configuration Parameters

The *variation of configuration parameters* provided an excellent possibility to generate solutions systematically. It has to be kept in mind that a huge amount of possible solutions is generated which afterwards has to be reduced. This reduction is not facile if the knowledge level of the properties is low in an early stage of the product development process.

A.2.7 Interviews

Interviews provide mostly qualitative information. They help to gain a understanding of the field but are not well suited to base decisions on them. The subjective influence of the interviewed person is difficult to take into account which prevents high quality results. Interviews are not recognised as a scientific source in all disciplines which arises the question if it is suitable for a Diploma Thesis. The share of information which were gained by interviews is substantial since only little information about the existing ground station has been documented.

A.3 System Description

Figure A-1.: *The subordinated elements of the kite power system*

Figure A-2.: *Elements of the ground station and their classification.*

Figure A-3.: *Elements of the power infrastructure*

Figure A-4.: Links between ground station elements. Not included are cables, beams, bearings, belt pulleys, stiffings, and the hard stop. The external elements tether and control stand are included to show connected elements. The 350 V DC-bus is a non-physical element.

A.4 Requirements

A.4.1 Checklist of Requirements

Hauptmerkmale	Beispiele
Geometrie	Größe, Höhe, Länge, Durchmesser, Raumbedarf, Anzahl, Anordnung, Anschluss, Ausbau und Erweiterung
Kinematik	Bewegungsart, Bewegungsrichtung, Geschwindigkeit, Beschleunigung
Kräfte	Kraftgröße, Kraftrichtung, Krafthäufigkeit, Gewicht, Last, Verformung, Steifigkeit, Federeigenschaften, Stabilität, Resonanzen, Dynamisches Verhalten
Energie	Leistung, Wirkungsgrad, Verlust, Reibung, Ventilation, Zustandsgrößen wie Druck, Temperatur, Feuchtigkeit, Erwärmung, Kühlung, Anschlussenergie, Speicherung, Arbeitsaufnahme, Energieumformung
Stoff	Physikalische, chemische, biologische Eigenschaften des Eingangs- und Ausgangsproduktes, Hilfsstoffe, vorgeschriebene Werkstoffe (Nahrungsmittelgesetze u. ä.), Materialtransport, Logistik
Signal	Eingangs- und Ausgangssignale, Anzeigeart, Betriebs- und Überwachungsgeräte, Signalform
Sicherheit	Unmittelbare Sicherheitstechnik, Schutzsysteme, Betriebs-, Arbeits- und Umweltsicherheit, CE-Sicherheitsiegel
Ergonomie	Mensch-Maschine-Beziehung: Bedienung, Bedienungsart, Übersichtlichkeit, Beleuchtung, Formgestaltung, Haptik, Gebrauchstauglichkeit
Fertigung	Einschränkung durch Produktionsstätte, größte herstellbare Abmessungen, bevorzugtes Fertigungsverfahren, Fertigungsmittel, mögliche Qualität und Toleranzen, Beschaffungsmöglichkeiten
Kontrolle	Prüfmöglichkeit, besondere Vorschriften (TÜV, ASME, DIN, ISO, CE, AD-Merkblätter)
Montage	Besondere Montagevorschriften, Zusammenbau, Einbau, Baustellenmontage, Fundamentierung, Inbetriebnahme, Endprüfung
Transport	Begrenzung durch Hebezeuge, Bahnprofil, Transportwege nach Größe und Gewicht, Versandart und -bedingungen, Container, Luftfracht
Gebrauch	Geräuscharmheit, Verschleißrate, Anwendung und Absatzgebiet, Einsatzort (z. B. schwefelige Atmosphäre, Tropen)
Instandhaltung	Wartungsfreiheit bzw. Anzahl und Zeitbedarf der Wartung, Inspektion, Austausch und Instandsetzung, Anstrich, Säuberung
Recycling	Wiederverwendung, Wiederverwertung, Weiterverwendung, Weiterverwertung, Endlagerung, Beseitigung
Kosten	Zul. Herstellkosten, Werkzeugkosten, Investition und Amortisation, Betriebskosten
Termin	Ende der Entwicklung, Netzplan für Zwischenschritte, Lieferzeit

Figure A-5.: Checklist for the definition of requirements

A.4.2 Purpose and Constraints

Figure A-6.: *Purpose and subpurposes of the ground station*

Figure A-7.: *Constraints of the ground station*

A.4.3 Interdependencies of Requirements

Requirements	#	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	
Use of a winch	1	■	0	0			0		0	0	0																		0	
Use of a tether	2		■	0	0	0				0																			0	
Drum geometry	3			■								+				+													0	
Geometry tether guidance	4				■	0			0	0																			0	
Releasable tether	5					■																					+			
Available torque	6						■				0													-		-				
Ground station auto-controllable	7							■	0	0											+			-		-			0	
Change direction of the drum	8								■	0		0												-		-			0	
Rotation speed	9									■		0										0							0	
Reduce losses	10										■		+					0					0						0	
Inertia / mass of the drum	11											■												0		0				
Redundance	12												■															+		
Display and track states	13													■														+		
Transportable	14														■															
Size of the ground station	15															■	+	+		+		+							0	
Weight of the ground station	16																■		-										0	
Use of generator	17																	■												
No special transportation permission needed	18																		■											-
Consideration of life cycle costs	19																				■									-
No grid connection	20																					■								+
Use of energy storage	21																						■							+
Consideration of costs of series production	22																							■						-
No launching and landing needed	23																								■					-
Consideration of costs of development	24																									■				+
Avoid damages	25																										■			+
Emergency stop	26																											■		+
Feeding mechanism	27																												■	
Li-batteries	28																												■	

Legend:

Varying interrelation	0
Positive	+
Negative	-
Is parent of	■

Figure A-8.: Interdependencies of requirements

A.5 Dependancy Matrix of Elements

In Table A-1 the influences are enlisted and the active sum, passive sum, activity, and criticality are calculated.

#	Element	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Active sum	Passive sum	Activity	Criticality
1	Tether guidance	X	1	1	0	1	3	0	0	0	6	3	2.0	18
2	Drive train	0	X	3	0	3	1	0	0	0	7	4	1.8	28
3	Body work	0	0	X	2	0	0	0	0	0	2	12	0.2	24
4	Trailer	0	0	2	X	0	0	0	0	0	2	3	0.7	6
5	Electrical machine	0	2	1	1	X	1	2	3	1	11	8	1.4	88
6	Sled	3	1	3	0	0	X	0	1	1	9	5	1.8	45
7	Energy Storage	0	0	1	0	1	0	X	3	1	6	4	1.5	24
8	Power infrastructure	0	0	1	0	2	0	1	X	1	5	8	0.6	40
9	IT infrastructure	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	X	3	4	0.8	12

Table A-1.: *Dependancy matrix*

The influences of the ground station elements on each other are scored according to Table A-2.

Description	Score
Strong influence	3
Moderate influence	2
Weak influence	1
No influence	0

Table A-2.: *Grading of influence*

A.6 Degrees of Freedom

Figure A-9.: *Degrees of freedom*

A.7 Relation Function Model

A.7.1 Development of the Relation Function Model

The *relation function model* is used to describe the subsystem ground station. It is built upon useful and adverse functions linked through relations (see Figure A-10).

Figure A-10.: *Elements and relations of the relation function model [Lin10]*

At first, the most obvious useful and adverse functions are defined and linked to each other (if possible). In Figure A-11, the first three useful and three adverse functions are shown¹.

Figure A-11.: *Relation function model of the ground station (Step 1)*

These functions are examined by addressing four questions, shown in Figure A-12, to each useful and adverse function accordingly to define new functions related to the existing ones.

¹If these functions are indeed objectively the most important one, can be discussed, but they represent a starting point.

Figure A-12.: *Questions to useful and adverse functions*

The supplemental functions are added and so the RPM develops step by step. This is done until all important functions of the subsystem ground station are found and linked to each other (see Figures A-13 , A-14, A-15, and A-16).

Figure A-13.: Relation function model of the ground station (Step 2)

Figure A-14.: Relation function model of the ground station (Step 3)

Figure A-15.: Relation function model of the ground station (Step 4)

A.7.3 Secondary Adverse Functions

Figure A-18.: *Secondary adverse functions and useful functions to avoid or reduce them*

A.7.4 Relation Function Model of the Generator Concept

Figure A-19.: The integration of the functions “increase rotation speed” and “decrease rotation speed” in the relation function model

A.7.5 Relation Function Model of the Tether Guidance

Figure A-20.: *Relation function model of the tether guidance*

A.8 Performance Factors

The following calculations are on basis of [FSO11].

$$D = \frac{t_{ro}}{t_{cyc}} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

D is the duty cycle, t_{ro} is the reel-out time and t_{ri} is the reel-in time.

$$t_{cyc} = t_{ro} + t_{ri} + t_{tr} \quad (\text{A.2})$$

t_{cyc} is the cycle time and t_{tr} is the sum of upper and lower transition time.

$$E_{mech,ro} = P_{mech,ro,avg} t_{ro} \quad (\text{A.3})$$

$E_{mech,ro}$ is the mechanical energy during reel-out, $P_{mech,ro,avg}$ is the average mechanical power during reel-out.

$$E_{mech,ri} = P_{mech,ri,avg} t_{ri} \quad (\text{A.4})$$

$E_{mech,ri} < 0$ is the mechanical energy during reel-in, $P_{mech,ri,avg} < 0$ is the average mechanical power during reel-in.

$$E_{mech,cyc} = E_{mech,ro} + E_{mech,ri} \quad (\text{A.5})$$

$E_{mech,cyc}$ is the energy balance of one cycle.

$$P_{mech,cyc,avg} = \frac{E_{mech,cyc}}{t_{cyc}} \quad (\text{A.6})$$

$P_{mech,cyc,avg}$ is the average mechanical power during one cycle.

$$\eta_{mech} = \frac{E_{mech,cyc}}{E_{mech,ro}} \quad (\text{A.7})$$

η_{mech} is the mechanical efficiency.

$$\eta_{cyc} = \frac{P_{mech,cyc,avg}}{P_{mech,ro,avg}} = D\eta_{mech} \quad (\text{A.8})$$

η_{cyc} is the cycle efficiency.

$$E_{mech,ro,EM} = E_{mech,ro} + E_{mech,ro,loss,DT} = \eta_{ro,DT,avg} E_{mech,ro} \quad (\text{A.9})$$

$E_{mech,ro,EM}$ is the mechanical energy put into the electrical machine during reel-out, $E_{mech,ro,loss,DT} < 0$ is the energy loss of the drive train during reel-out, $\eta_{ro,DT,avg}$ is the average efficiency of the drive train during reel-out.

$$E_{el,ro,EM} = E_{mech,ro,EM} + E_{el,ro,loss,EM} = \eta_{ro,EM,avg} E_{mech,ro,EM} \quad (A.10)$$

$E_{el,ro,EM}$ is the electrical energy generated by the electrical machine during the reel-out, $E_{el,ro,loss,EM} < 0$ is the energy loss of the electrical machine during reel-out, $\eta_{ro,EM,avg}$ is the average efficiency of the electrical machine during reel-out.

$$E_{mech,ri,EM} = E_{mech,ri} + E_{mech,ri,loss,DT} = \eta_{ro,DT,avg} E_{mech,ro} \quad (A.11)$$

$E_{mech,ri,EM}$ is the mechanical energy delivered by the electrical machine during reel-in, $E_{mech,ri,loss,DT} < 0$ is the energy loss of the drive train during reel-in, $\eta_{ro,DT,avg}$ is the average efficiency of the drive train during reel-in.

$$E_{el,ri,EM} = E_{mech,ri,EM} - E_{el,ri,loss,EM} = \eta_{ri,EM,avg} E_{mech,ri,EM} \quad (A.12)$$

$E_{el,ri,EM}$ is the electrical energy consumed by the electrical machine during reel-in, $E_{el,ri,loss,EM} < 0$ is the the energy loss of the electrical machine during reel-in, $\eta_{ri,EM,avg}$ is the average efficiency of the electrical machine during reel-in.

$$\eta_{BAT,avg} = \frac{E_{el,out,BAT}}{E_{el,in,BAT}} \quad (A.13)$$

$\eta_{BAT,avg}$ is the average battery efficiency, $E_{el,out,BAT}$ is the energy output of the battery, $E_{el,in,BAT}$ is the energy input into the battery.

$$E_{el,loss,BAT} = E_{el,out,BAT} - E_{el,in,BAT} \quad (A.14)$$

$E_{el,loss,BAT} < 0$ is the energy loss of the battery during cycle.

$$E_{el,out,BAT} = E_{el,ri,EM} \quad (A.15)$$

$$E_{el,gro} = E_{el,ro,EM} + E_{el,ri} + E_{el,loss,BAT} = E_{el,ro,EM} + \frac{E_{el,ri}}{\eta_{BAT,avg}} \quad (A.16)$$

$E_{el,gro}$ is the gross electrical energy during cycle.

$$E_{el,net} = E_{el,gro} + E_{el,loss,SPDL} + E_{el,loss,BRK} + E_{el,loss,INV} = \eta_{SYS} E_{el,gro} \quad (A.17)$$

$E_{el,net}$ is the net electrical energy during cycle, $E_{el,loss,SPDL} < 0$ is the energy consumed to drive the spindle motor, $E_{el,loss,BRK} < 0$ is the energy consumed to activate the brakes, $E_{el,loss,INV} < 0$ is the energy consumed by the inverter, η_{SYS} is the sytem efficiency.

$$\eta_{tot} = \frac{E_{el,net}}{E_{mech,ro}} \quad (A.18)$$

η_{tot} is the total efficiency.

In Figure A-21 the energies are shown.

Figure A-21.: Definition of energies, based on [FSO11]

A.9 Generator Concept - Calculations

The drum speed is:

$$n_D = \frac{v_T}{\pi d_D} \cdot \frac{60s}{1min} \quad (\text{A.19})$$

The mechanical power at the drum is calculated by:

$$P_{mech} = 2\pi T \frac{n}{\frac{60s}{1min}} \frac{1kW}{1000W} \quad (\text{A.20})$$

where n is the rotation speed (rpm) and T is the torque (Nm).

$$n_D = \frac{v_T}{\pi d_D} \cdot \frac{60s}{1min} \quad (\text{A.21})$$

where n_D is the rotation speed of the drum (rpm).

$$n_{D,ri,max} = \frac{-14m/s}{\pi 0.3m} \cdot \frac{60s}{1min} \approx -892rpm \quad (\text{A.22})$$

$$n_{D,ro,max} = \frac{8m/s}{\pi 0.3m} \cdot \frac{60s}{1min} \approx 510rpm \quad (\text{A.23})$$

$$T_D = 1/2 F_T \cdot d_D \quad (\text{A.24})$$

where T_D is the torque at the drum.

$$T_{D,min} = 1/2 \cdot 800N \cdot 0.3m = 120Nm \quad (\text{A.25})$$

$$T_{D,max} = 1/2 \cdot 11,000N \cdot 0.3m = 1,650Nm \quad (\text{A.26})$$

$$P_{mech,ro,nom} = C_{mech,ro} \cdot P_{mech,ro,avg} = 1.5 \cdot 50kW = 75kW \quad (\text{A.27})$$

The crest factor $C_{mech,ro}$ is assumed at 1.5 [Fec11b].

A.10 Electrical Machines Types

Figure A-22.: *Hierarchy of electrical machine types*

A.11 Compatibility Matrices of Partial Solutions of the Generator Concept

In Tables A-3, A-4, and A-5, the compatibilities of partial solutions are indicated to either favorable (+) or unfavorable (-).

		Type	
		SCIM	PMSM
Gearbox	Mechanical	-	-
	Direct-drive	+	+

Table A-3.: *Compatibility matrix for the electrical machine in the REM concept*

		Type	
		SCIM	PMSM
Gearbox	Mechanical	-	-
	Direct-drive	+	+

Table A-4.: *Compatibility matrix for the generator in the CGCM concept*

		Type	
		SCIM	PMSM
Gearbox	Mechanical	-	-
	Direct-drive	+	+

Table A-5.: *Compatibility matrix for the motor in the CGCM concept*

A.12 Tether Diagrams

Figure A-23.: *Breaking strength of Dyneema*

Figure A-24.: *Specific weight of Dyneema*

Figure A-25.: *Endurance of Dyneema*

Figure A-26.: *Bending cycles for Dyneema*

A.13 Tether Guidance Concept - Calculations

Bending stress as function of the bending diameter:

$$\sigma_x(y) = \frac{y + \frac{1}{2}d_B}{\frac{1}{2}d_B} \sigma_x(0) \quad (\text{A.28})$$

Tether diameter (mm)	Nominal breaking load (kN)
4	13
5	26
6	40
8	81

Table A-6.: Tether diameter and corresponding nominal breaking loads [DYN]

The capacity of the (storage) drum:

$$V_T = d_D \pi w_D N d_T = l_t \frac{d_T^2}{2} \pi \quad (\text{A.29})$$

where V_T is the tether volume, d_D is the average drum diameter, w_D is the drum width, N is the number of layers, d_T is the tether diameter, and l_t is the length of the tether.

The power loss of the swivel P_{SW} is calculated to:

$$P_{SW} = v_T F_f \quad (\text{A.30})$$

where v_T is the tether speed and F_f is the frictional force.

$$F_f = \mu F_N \quad (\text{A.31})$$

The normal force \vec{F}_N is:

$$\vec{F}_N = \vec{F}_{T,0} + \vec{F}_{T,1} \quad (\text{A.32})$$

where $\vec{F}_{T,0}$ is the tether force outside of the ground station and $\vec{F}_{T,1}$ is the tether force after the swivel (inside the ground station). In scalars this equation can be written as:

$$F_N = \sqrt{\cos^2(F_{T_0}) + (\sin(\theta) \cdot F_{T_0} - F_{T,1})^2} \quad (\text{A.33})$$

where θ is the elevation angle of the kite.

It follows:

$$P_{SW} = \mu v_T \sqrt{\cos^2(F_{T_0}) + (\sin(\theta) \cdot F_{T_0} - F_{T,1})^2} \quad (\text{A.34})$$

A.14 Variations of Tether Guidance Elements

Category	No.	Property	Drum	Fairlead	Swivel	Pulley
Surfaces and bodies	1	Shape	X	X	X	X
	2	Location	X	X	X	X
	3	Number	X			X
	4	Size	X			X
Relations to tether	5	Connection type				
	6	Contact type	X	X	X	X
	7	Coupling type	X	X	X	X
	8	Interconnection structure				
	9	Sequential arrangement				
	10	Compactness	X			
Production referral attributes	11	Material	X	X	X	X
	12	Manufacturing process				
Movements	13	Reference system				
	14	Movement type	X	X		
	15	Path of movement				
	16	Joint freedom	X	X	X	X
Inversion	17	Negation		X	X	X

Table A-7.: *Variation parameters of the tether guidance*

Property	Considered	Possibilities			
Shape - drum		Cylindrical	Hyperboloid	Conic	Double-conic
Shape - surface		plain	grooved - normal	V-grooved	
Location	X	horizontally with axis along trailer	horizontally with axis cross the trailer	vertically	other
Number	X	One drum	One capstan and one storage drum	One double capstan and one storage drum	
Size		Minimum size dependent on bending radius	Maximum radius dependent on transportability		
Contact type		surface contact			
Coupling type		Roll	Roll and slide		
Compactness		Full material	Hollow	Open	
Material		Steel	Alloy	Composite	
Movement type	X	Only rotation around axis	Rotation and axially movement	Rotation around axis and perpendicular to axis	Two rotations and axially
Joint freedom		One rotatory	One rotatory and one axially	2 rotatory	2 rotatory and one translatory

Table A-8.: *Drum variations*

Property	Considered	Possibilities				
Shape	X	Four pulleys	Two pulleys	bell mouth		
Location	X	Attached to the drum	Disconnected from the drum			
Material		Steel	Alloy	Rubber surface ... on steel		
Movement type	X	Static	1 translational	2 translational		
Joint freedom		None	1 transl.	1 rot., 1 transl.	2 rot.	2 rot., 1 transl.
Negation	X	Fairlead used	No fairlead used			

Table A-9.: *Fairlead variations*

Property	Considered	Possibilities			
Shape	X	Four pulleys	Two pulleys	Bell mouth	
Location	X	Top of the ground station	Side of the ground station		
Coupling type		Rolling	Gliding	Rolling and gliding	
Material		Steel	Alloy	Rubber surface on steel	
Joint freedom		None	1 rotational	1 rotational, 1 translational	2 rotational
Negation		Swivel used	No swivel used		

Table A-10.: *Swivel variations*

Property	Considered	Possibilities			
Shape		Cylindrical	Hyperboloid	Conic	Double-conic
Location		Generates 90° rope angel	Generates 180° rope angel	Generates different rope angel	
Number	X	1	2	...	
Size		small	medium	big	
Contact type		convex - planar	convex - concave		
Coupling type		Rolling	Gliding	Rolling and gliding	
Material		Steel	Alloy	Rubber surface on steel	
Joint freedom		1 rotational	2 rotational	3 rotational	
Negation	X	pulley(s) used	no pulley used		

Table A-11.: *Pulley variations*

A.15 Cycle Model

Assumptions:

- wind is laminar not turbulent and constant,
- direction of the kite is always down wind (azimuth angle is 0°),
- tether angle is neglected.

Reel-out:

$$F_{T,ro} = \frac{1}{2}\rho_L S_{proj} v_{app,ro}^2 \quad (\text{A.35})$$

$$v_{app,ro} = \frac{L}{D}(v_W - v_T) \quad (\text{A.36})$$

$$F_{T,ro} = \frac{1}{2}\rho_L S_{proj} \left(\frac{L}{D}\right)^2 (v_W - v_T)^2 \quad (\text{A.37})$$

$$P_T = F_t v_T \quad (\text{A.38})$$

$$P_{T,ro} = \frac{1}{2}\rho_L S_{proj} \left(\frac{L}{D}\right)^2 (v_W - v_T)^2 v_T \quad (\text{A.39})$$

The power of the tether is equal to the power at the drum (losses of drum bearings are neglected.)

$$P_D = P_T \quad (\text{A.40})$$

$$P_D = \omega T \quad (\text{A.41})$$

$$\omega = 2\pi n \quad (\text{A.42})$$

$$P_D = 2\pi n T \quad (\text{A.43})$$

Because it common to use the unit “rpm” for rotation speeds:

$$P_D = 2\pi \frac{n}{60s/min} T \quad (\text{A.44})$$

Reel-in:

$$F_T = \frac{1}{2} \rho S_{proj} C_D v_{app,ri}^2 \quad (\text{A.45})$$

where C_D is the drag coefficient of the kite (the drag of the tether is neglected).

$$v_{app,ri} = v_W - v_T \quad (\text{A.46})$$

where $v_T < 0$.

$$F_T = \frac{1}{2} \rho S_{proj} C_D (v_W - v_T)^2 \quad (\text{A.47})$$

$$P_T = \frac{1}{2} \rho S_{proj} C_D (v_W - v_T)^2 v_T \quad (\text{A.48})$$

where P_T is < 0 .

$$P_{cyc} = \frac{P_{T,ro} * t_{ro} + P_{T,ri} * t_{ri}}{t_{ro} + t_{ri}} \quad (\text{A.49})$$

Figure A-27.: Average mechanical power (kW) for one cycle as function of the reel-out and reel-in speed of the tether for a nominal wind speed of 9.5 m/s.

A.16 Properties of Electrical Machines

Property	FKI 250 M2	FKI 250 M4	FKI 280 M6	FKI 315 S8	B4C 315 MA10	315 MC12
P_{nom} (kW)	55	55	55	55	55	55
p (-)	2	4	6	8	10	12
n_{nom} (rpm)	2,955	1,475	980	735	590	490
T_{nom} (Nm)	178	356	535	714	889	1,071
T_{max} (Nm)	534	926	1,391	1,571	2,311	2,678
η (%)	93	93.7	92.8	93.0	92.0	92.0
m (kg)	225	264	353	459	735	815
Costs (Euro)	1,526	1,662	3,234	4,890	6,159	6,868
f_{max} (Hz)	60	75	75	75	75	75
n_{max} (rpm)	3,546	2,212.5	1,470	1,102.5	885	735
i_{max}	1 : 6.95	1 : 4.34	1 : 2.88	1 : 2.16	1 : 1.74	1 : 1.44
i_{min}	1 : 3.09	1 : 1.78	1 : 1.19	1 : 1.05	1 : 0.71	1 : 0.62

Table A-12.: *Properties of SCIM generators*

Property	Alxion 500STK8M	Alxion 800STK2M	Alxion 800STK4M
P_{nom} (kW)	46.6	43.9	77.1
p (-)	36	48	48
n_{nom} (rpm)	400	400	400
T_{nom} (Nm)	1,197	1,135	1,986
η (%)	93	93	94.0
m (kg)	133	82	138
Costs (Euro)	10,600	*	16,400
f_{max} (Hz)	60	60	60
n_{max} (rpm)	480	480	480
i_{max}	1 : 0.94	1 : 0.94	1 : 0.94
i_{min}	1 : 1.38	1 : 1.45	1 : 0.83

Table A-13.: *Properties of PMSM generators(* Price has not been inquired)*

Property	FKI 180 M2	FKI 180 L4	FKI 200 LB6	FKI 225 M8
P_{nom} (kW)	22	22	22	22
p (-)	2	4	6	8
n_{nom} (rpm)	2,930	1,465	970	730
T_{nom} (Nm)	72	143	216	288
T_{max} (Nm)	216	358	518	691
η (%)	90.8	90.8	89.4	88.9
m (kg)	98	122	145	220
Costs (Euro)	744	*	1,302	1,903
f_{max} (Hz)	60	75	75	75
n_{max} (rpm)	3,516	2,197.5	1,455	1,095
i_{max}	1 : 3.94	1 : 2.46	1 : 1.63	1 : 1.23
i_{min}	1 : 1.91	1 : 1.15	1 : 0.8	1 : 0.6

Table A-14.: *Properties of SCIM motors (* Price has not been inquired)*

Property	Alxion 300STK8M	Alxion 400STK3M	Alxion 500STK2M	Alxion 800STK1M
P_{nom} (kW)	19.4	23.1	22.7	22.7
p (-)	24	24	48	48
n_{nom} (rpm)	600	800	600	400
T_{nom} (Nm)	348	297	396	611
η (%)	92	92	91	89.0
m (kg)	57	46	43	55
Costs (Euro)	*	*	4,500	*
f_{max} (Hz)	60	75	75	75
n_{max} (rpm)	720	1200	900	600
i_{max}	1 : 0.81	1 : 1.35	1 : 1.01	1 : 0.67
i_{min}	1 : 1.18	1 : 1.39	1 : 1.04	1 : 0.67

Table A-15.: *Properties of PMSM motors (* Price has not been inquired)*

The power rating of the electrical machines have to be higher than 50 kW for the generator mode and approximately 20 kW for motor mode.

The maximum reel-out torque $T_{ro,max}$, the maximum reel-out speed n_{ro} , and the maximum reel-in speed n_{ri} are taken from Section 3.1.2. The maximum reel-in torque $T_{ri,max}$ is calculated on basis of the the reel-in speed of the tether v_{ri} of 7.1 m/s at a wind speed v_W of 9.5 m/s to 412 Nm.

$$T_{ri,max} = \frac{d_D}{2} F_{T,max} = \frac{d_D}{2} \cdot \frac{1}{2} \rho S - proj C_D (v_W - v_{ri})^2 T_{ri,max} = 412 Nm \quad (A.50)$$

The maximal frequency of the motor controller f_{max} is given for the squirrel cage induction machines with more than two poles with 75 Hz. If not specified it assumed with 60 Hz [Gra94, p. 19]². The speed of the rotor is proportional to the frequency of the motor controller.

Figure A-28.: V/f -curve for the use of a motor controller [PNP04, p. 16]

$$i = \frac{n_{input}}{n_{output}} \quad (A.51)$$

The minimum transmission i_{min} is calculated by:

$$i_{min} = \frac{T_{ro,max}}{T_{EM,max}} \quad (A.52)$$

where $T_{ro,max}$ is the maximum torque during reel-out at the drum and $T_{EM,max}$ is the maximum torque of the electrical machine.

The maximum transmission i_{max} is calculated by:

²There is no obvious reason why the frequency cannot be higher. The only limit is the centrifugal forces on the structure. There are applications known where the frequency can be three times to ten times higher [Ige11].

$$i_{max} = \frac{n_{EM,max}}{n_{ro,max}} \quad (\text{A.53})$$

where $n_{EM,max}$ is the maximum rotation speed of the and $n_{ro,max}$ is the maximum rotation speed of the drum during reel-out.

Some of the electrical machines have a minimum transmission ration which is higher than the maximum transmission. Those machines cannot fulfill both requirements of the maximum torque and maximum speed with the same gearbox and are therefore discarded.

A.17 Schemes

A.17.1 Schemes of Generator Concepts

Figure A-29.: Generator concept with one direct-driven squirrel cage induction machine

Figure A-30.: Generator concept with two direct-driven squirrel cage induction machines

Figure A-31.: Generator concept with two mechanically geared squirrel cage induction machines

Figure A-32.: Generator concept with two direct-driven permanent magnet synchronous machines

A.17.2 Schemes of Tether Guidance Concepts

Figure A-33.: Scheme of the single capstan concept

Figure A-34.: Scheme of the double capstan concept

Figure A-35.: *Scheme of the simple drum concept*

Figure A-36.: *Scheme of the spiral drum concept*

A.18 Product Life Cycle

Figure A-37.: Product life cycle reference model [HTML09, p. 6]

A.19 Pictures of the Existing Kite Power System

Figure A-38.: *Picture of the tether and kite control unit*

Figure A-39.: *Picture of the swivel*

Figure A-40.: *Picture of the swivel, tether, and kite [Der]*

Figure A-41.: *Picture of the pulley*

Figure A-42.: *Picture of the ground station 1*

Figure A-43.: *Picture of the ground station 2*

Figure A-44.: *Picture of the ground station 3*

Figure A-45.: *Picture of the sled*

Figure A-46.: *Picture of the spindle motor*

Figure A-47.: *Picture of the control stand*